

Planning Prophecy

Trends in Undergraduate Research in
Urban and Regional Planning

Volume 1, April 2026

Department of Urban and Regional Planning
Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Khulna -9203

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The Department of Urban and Regional Planning at Khulna University of Engineering and Technology (KUET) is launching the **inaugural issue** of its annual publication, a fully peer-reviewed collection of undergraduate thesis abstracts. This landmark first volume showcases high-quality research from various universities, centering on pivotal topics within urban and regional planning. By establishing this rigorous academic platform, the department aims to highlight the intellectual contributions of emerging planners while fostering a collaborative research culture across institutions. As the first of its kind for the department, this publication serves as both a historical milestone and a vital resource for scholars and practitioners tracking the future of spatial development.

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Impacts of 2D And 3d Urban Morphology on Land Surface Temperature across Urban Functional Zones: A Case Study of Chattogram, Bangladesh

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Keywords

Land surface temperature, Urban morphology, Urban functional zones, Urban heat mitigation.

1. Introduction

The Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect has been intensified by rapid urbanization in tropical South Asian cities, posing threat to public health, energy effectiveness, and urban livability. In, Chattogram, the main seaport city of Bangladesh, where the vertical and horizontal growth have redesigned the microclimates and contributed to increase the surface temperature (Naim & Kafy, 2021). Prior studies conducted over the region have focused mainly on relation between LULC and LST, but few have used the detailed 3D urban morphology and functional zoning, despite the fact that both are significantly effective on the surface thermal patterns (Mo et al., 2024). The objective of the study to incorporate high-resolution remote sensing, 3D city modeling, as well as advanced spatial-statistical analysis which will provide zone-based observations that will guide sustainable urban planning.

2. Materials and Methods

The methodological Framework is illustrated in Figure 1. The study area consists of 5 thanas (Pahartali, Haliashahar, Khulshi, Double Mooring, and Kotwali). For increased precision, LST was retrieved from Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS Level-2 Surface Temperature using the Improved Mono-Window (IMW) algorithm with NDVI based emissivity and atmospheric transmittance correction. Urban Functional Zones were defined based on Voronoi polygons generated from road intersections and assigned by prevalent land use types (Figure 2).

Building footprint and height data were used to compute Urban morphological parameters which were collected from Chattogram Development Authority (CDA). Two dimensional indices, i.e., Building Density (BD) and Landscape Shape Index (LSI) and three-dimensional indices i.e. Height Standard Deviation (HSD), Mean Building Height (MBH), Mean Building

Volume (MBV), Floor Area Ratio (FAR), Space Crowding (SCD), and Coefficient of Variation (CV), were incorporated in the study (Li et al., 2021, Labetski et al., 2023). Sun Shadow Volume tool was used to take shading into account. Building shadows were simulated, and tree shading was approximated after NDVI thresholding. Area Solar Radiation was used to calculate solar energy absorbed throughout the study.

Fig 1. Methodological Framework

A detailed morphological and radiative analysis was done, A 3D digital city was digitized using building footprint layer and a vegetation layer. Data analytical techniques included One-Way ANOVA (in testing variation in LST across UFZs), Pearson correlation, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Spatial Lag Model (SLM) and Gradient Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) with 10-fold cross-validation to account for non-linear, zone-specific effects. BRT was chosen due to its ability to predict outcomes across different UFZs while capturing non-linear relationship between LST and Morphological matrices.

3. Results and Discussion

Significant variations were observed in land surface temperature (LST) between urban forest zones (UFZs) (ANOVA $F = 19.86, p < 0.05$). Table 1 shows industrial districts had the maximum mean LST (34.9 °C) due to their densely covered surface with minimal green cover, while ecological districts were the coolest (32.6 °C).

Fig 2. Study area – (a) UFZ, (b) LST

Table 1. LST in different UFZs

Urban Functional Zone	n	$\bar{x} \pm \sigma$
Commercial Zone	38	33.7 ± 0.62
Ecological Zone	141	32.6 ± 1.14
Industrial Zone	37	34.9 ± 1.16
Mixed Zone	99	33.9 ± 0.80
Public Zone	217	32.9 ± 0.87
Residential Zone	445	32.4 ± 0.82
Traffic Zone	45	32.7 ± 0.81

The result for correlations (Figure 3) indicated that BD and solar radiation had a very strong association with LST, indicating that densely planned areas and exposure to sunlight lead to a rise in temperature. In contrast, HSD had a negative association with LST, indicating that higher buildings provide more shading effect and enhancing wind flow. SHADE was found to have a positive link with LST in many areas. This means that thick, canyon-like shade might limit airflow and hold in longwave radiation instead of letting heat escape.

Fig 3. Pearson correlation between building morphology metrics and LST in all UFZs (Significant correlation

at 0.01 level were labeled with ** ($p < 0.01$), those at 0.05 level were labeled with * ($p < 0.05$))

From the models Comparison, it was showed that BRT significantly outperformed OLS and SLM in predictions (R^2 up to 0.93 in traffic zones), and SLM successfully captured spatial dependency. Followed by HSD and MBV, BD was always the best estimator across all zones, with their influence depending on the situation. Marginal effects were shown using Partial Dependence Plots. In most of the zones, BD, SOLAR and HSD were the main features to predict the outcomes. By illuminating the nonlinear and particular morphological temperature interaction behavior, the results highlight the need for context specific rather than general heat mitigation policy interventions recommending solutions for height variation and density management.

4. Conclusion

To clarify how heat functions in study area, the analysis formulates a robust framework that connects improved LST recovery, 2D/3D shape estimations, and modeling according to urban functional zones. The findings reveal that building density and solar radiation correspond with higher heat, while variation in building heights and shapes can mitigate it under certain conditions. The positive correlation between shade and LST reveals the complexity of 3D cityscapes. Furthermore, the research also highlights the necessity that heat mitigation must be zone sensitive with density and volume control in the industrial zones, preservation of ecological zones, and vertical diversity in both residential and commercial areas. For tropical cities, the framework offers a transferrable climate-responsive planning framework.

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Urban Transformation in the 21st Century: Comparative SSP-Guided Land Use Modelling of Dhaka, Mumbai, and New York

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Keywords

Land use, Machine learning, Shared socio-economic pathways, Urban growth

1. Introduction

Rapid urbanization across the globe is reshaping land use patterns, intensifying pressure on ecosystems, and challenging urban sustainability. Cities such as Dhaka, Mumbai, and New York represent a spectrum from least developed to developed contexts, each facing unique challenges, where socioeconomic dynamics, population density, and regulatory frameworks govern land transformation processes. Global projections indicate that urban land will expand significantly by mid-century, emphasizing the need for city-specific scenario modeling to anticipate future transitions (Chen et al., 2020). Despite considerable research on land use/land cover (LULC) change, the integration of Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs) within machine learning-based frameworks remain limited, particularly for comparative studies involving a spectrum from least developed to developed contexts. This study therefore aims to model and compare future LULC patterns in Dhaka, Mumbai, and New York using a hybrid machine learning-XGBoost-CA-Markov approach under five SSPs, evaluating their implications for urban sustainability and spatial resilience.

2. Materials and Methods

A hybrid machine learning model combining hierarchical Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Cellular Automata (CA), and Markov Chain modeling was developed. This integrated framework captures both the transition probabilities and the spatial allocation of land use dynamics. Historical LULC data for 2017, 2020, and 2023 were derived from Sentinel-2-based Esri datasets at 10 m resolution and classified into seven classes: water, trees, flooded vegetation, crops, built area, bare ground, and rangeland. Socio-economic drivers such as population and GDP were sourced from the SSP databases, while topographic

and accessibility factors (elevation, slope, road proximity, and transport hub distance) were included as explanatory variables. The hierarchical classifier first separated natural and anthropogenic transitions to mitigate class imbalance, then used sub-models for detailed classification. Transition probabilities were computed using Markov analysis, while CA allocated future land use according to spatial contiguity and neighborhood influence. SSP-specific multipliers represented variations in economic growth, environmental protection, and spatial compactness across the five pathways. Temporal validation used the 2017-2020 period for training and the independent 2020-2023 period for testing, ensuring evaluation on temporally distinct data. Train and test samples were also spatially distinct from each other. Model performance was assessed using comprehensive metrics including accuracy, Kappa coefficient, F1-scores weighted by class prevalence, and Figure of Merit.

Fig 1: Methodological Framework

3. Results and Discussion

The hybrid model achieved robust performance across all study areas with accuracies ranging from 92% to 98% and Kappa coefficients between 0.87 and 0.96. The F1-scores above 0.8 confirmed the model's stability for heterogeneous urban forms. Projected results revealed accelerated urban expansion in Dhaka and Mumbai through 2050, particularly under SSP3 and SSP5, while New York's built-up extent plateaued beyond mid-century. In Dhaka, built-up areas are expected to occupy 64–68% of total land by 2050, primarily replacing croplands and vegetation, consistent with Hossein et al. (2023). Mumbai's urban footprint will increase to 55–64%, consuming rangelands and

peripheral agriculture (Vinayak et al., 2021). Conversely, New York’s built-up share will grow modestly by only 1.4–2.9%, stabilizing after 2075 due to stringent zoning and infrastructure maturity. Comparative SSP analysis indicated that Dhaka and Mumbai exhibit high sensitivity to socio-economic drivers, where built area growth under SSP5 (fossil-fueled development) exceeds that under SSP1 (sustainability) by 7.7% and 24.5%, respectively. The findings underline that cities in the Global South are more responsive to population and GDP pressures than developed cities with regulated land management regimes. The model validation against literature demonstrates high coherence, affirming its reliability for scenario-based planning.

4. Conclusion

This study advances a data-driven, scenario-based modeling approach integrating machine learning with socio-economic narratives to forecast long-term urban expansion. The hybrid XGBoost–CA–Markov framework effectively merges probabilistic transition modeling with spatial dynamics, offering scalable applications for comparative urban studies. Findings emphasize the urgent need for strategic land management in Dhaka and Mumbai to prevent the loss of agricultural and ecological lands, which are projected to be the primary sources of urban growth. In contrast, New York’s relatively stable pattern highlights the role of mature governance and zoning control. By aligning urban modeling with SSP narratives, this study contributes a replicable methodology for integrating socio-economic foresight into spatial planning. The results serve as a vital tool for policymakers to design adaptive urban growth strategies under uncertain future pathways.

Fig 2: Future Land Use Projection of (a) Dhaka, (b) Mumbai and (c) New York

Fig 3: Built Area Growth Trend in (a) Dhaka, (b) Mumbai and (c) New York

Fig 4: Sources of Built Area Growth in (a) Dhaka, (b) Mumbai and (c) New York

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Citizen Participation in Urban Governance: A Case of Grievance Reporting System in Khulna City

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Keywords

Citizen participation, Grievance reporting system, Participatory GIS, Urban governance.

1. Introduction

Urban governance, defined as the management of cities concerning community involvement and service provision (Hosseinzadeh et al., 2015; Obeng-Odoom, 2012), often faces challenges in rapidly urbanizing regions like secondary cities in Bangladesh. Governance systems are frequently criticized for being non-transparent and inefficient, leading to fragmented services and diminished public trusts (Denters & Klok, 2010). Participatory Geographic Information Systems (PGIS) offer a solution by enabling citizens to map and report urban issues in real-time, thereby enhancing accountability and inclusivity (Slaev et al., 2019).

The objective of this research is to develop and test a web-based PGIS platform for community-based problem reporting in Khulna city, specifically to improve citizen participation and spatial transparency in urban governance.

This study fills a critical research and policy gap in South Asia by applying PGIS to grievance reporting. It offers a practical model for institutions like the Khulna City Corporation to transition from fragmented, bureaucratic complaint handling to a modern, responsive, and data-driven system, thereby fostering more inclusive urban development.

2. Materials and Methods

The methodology involved a multi-phased approach combining system development and empirical evaluation. The process commenced with reviewing existing e-services to identify gaps and determine the scope by identifying problems & authorities relevant to Khulna city (KCC, KDA, KMP, KWASA, Fire Service).

The system development was guided by a formal System Design phase, splitting into frontend and backend construction. The frontend was developed using React.js for the User Interface (UI) and utilized Leaflet.js to integrate map-based functionality. This interface was designed to Integrate Rest API endpoints and was ultimately bundled using Vite. Concurrently, the

Backend was built with a server Created with Express.js and running on Node.js to provide the Rest API. Data persistence and structure were defined using a MongoDB Schema.

Fig 1. Methodological framework

Following the Deployment of the web-based system, its effectiveness and technical performance were empirically validated. Data was collected by conducting surveys, which was then subjected to descriptive analysis, including frequency distribution, reliability analysis (Cronbach's Alpha) and graphical representation to interpret user participations.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Barriers to effective complaint management

A significant majority of respondents, particularly students and professionals, expressed frustration over the lack of follow-up and unclear reporting channels, citing that complaints often went unresolved or were never acknowledged, highlighting the need for a more transparent and citizen-friendly system that allows users to track the progress of their complaints and engage meaningfully with service providers.

Fig 2. Challenges faced by respondents

3.2. PGIS Development

To address these gaps, a dual-interface PGIS platform was developed, enabling citizens to report service issues with geospatial precision while allowing authorities to view, filter, and respond through an administrative dashboard. A modal form for problem reporting lets user lodge their complaints.

Fig 3. (a) Main interface, (b) Modal form of problem reporting and (c) Heatmap

The heatmap visualization generated from user-submitted data revealed spatial clustering of service delivery problems, particularly in drainage, waste management, and road maintenance. This spatial insight offers a valuable tool for municipal authorities to prioritize interventions based on geographic concentration of grievances.

Fig 4. (a) Problem management and (b) Citizen's Feedback window

3.3. Evaluation

Technical evaluation using Google Lighthouse showed that the platform is well-optimized for mobile-first users, with an overall performance score of 88/100.

Key metrics such as Largest Contentful Paint (LCP ~3.6s), minimal Total Blocking Time (TBT), and stable Cumulative Layout Shift (CLS) confirm that the system is fast, responsive, and visually stable. These results validate the platform's readiness for real-world deployment in urban Bangladesh. (Include: Figure 5 – Technical performance metrics)

Conclusion

The study's contributions and potential applications are significant. The PGIS platform introduced a transparent and spatially precise system for grievance reporting, effectively addressing the limitations of existing fragmented mechanisms. Pilot testing demonstrated strong usability and a high potential for user adoption, further supported by reliable technical performance optimized for mobile-first users. Overall, the approach presents a scalable model for participatory urban governance in cities, enhancing accountability and fostering meaningful citizen engagement.

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Hierarchical Stream Classification and Prediction of Bankline Shifting of Brahmaputra River in Bangladesh

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Keywords

Bankline shifting, Brahmaputra River, erosion–accretion, stream classification

1. Introduction

The Brahmaputra River, one of South Asia’s largest and most dynamic river systems, is vital for livelihoods but highly vulnerable to erosion and channel migration (Bhuyan et al., 2023). This study classifies its hierarchical stream network, evaluates bankline changes between 1995 and 2025, and forecasts shifts up to 2045. These insights are critical for designing adaptive management strategies to reduce risks and promote sustainable river governance. The objectives of the study are to classify the hierarchical stream of Brahmaputra River, to quantify riverbank shifting patterns between 1995 to 2025, and to predict future bankline position up to 2045.

2. Materials and Methods

Multi-temporal satellite imagery, Landsat (30 m), Sentinel-2 (10m) and SRTM DEM were processed at 10-year temporal interval in ArcGIS to extract river networks and banklines.

Fig 1: Zones of The River Used in Analysis

Stream order classification was conducted using the Strahler method (Valjarević, 2024). Bankline dynam-

ics were quantified through the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) using End Point Rate (EPR) and Linear Regression Rate (LRR). A total of 752 transects across five river zones were analyzed, and predictive models were applied to estimate future bankline positions.

3. Results and Discussion

Observed Bankline Changes (1995–2025):

Fig 2: Temporal Assessment of Riverbank Shifting Using the DSAS Model

Zone 1 consistently showed severe left bank retreat (up to -84 m/year), while the right bank alternated between erosion and deposition, reflecting channel curvature and monsoonal controls. Zone 2 displayed mixed dynamics, including substantial right bank accretion ($+47.18$ m/year), comparable to localized depositional features in the Padma River (Arefin et al., 2021). Zones 3 and 4 were the most unstable, with erosion rates exceeding those reported for several Himalayan-fed rivers, while Zone 5 showed persistent deposition linked to char land formation.

Predicted Bankline Changes (2025–2045):

Based on LRR derived trends, projected bankline positions for 2025-2045 indicate continues erosion dominance in Zone 1 and 4 and sustained deposition in Zone 5. These projected trends are consistent with predictive modeling results from other monsoon-driven rivers such as Ganga and Teesta (Hasan et al., 2024). However, as shown in studies of Subarnarekha River (Jana, 2021), depositional reaches may remain morphologically unstable over time, suggesting that predicted stability zones should be interpreted with caution.

Fig 3: Temporal Prediction of Riverbank Shifting Using the DSAS Model: 2025-2045

Spatial overlays highlight erosion-prone left banks in Shivalaya, Kalihati, Bera, Belkuchi, Shahjadpur, and Phulchhari, and right bank hotspots in Islampur, Tangail S., Phulchhari, Sughatta, Raomari, and Kalihati. Future pathways suggest mixed erosion-accretion trends in Baksiganj, Dewanganj, Nagarpur, and Chauhali.

Fig 4: Key Upazilas Experiencing Significant Erosion-Accretion Dynamics

Based on LRR and DSAS outputs, each Brahmaputra zone requires tailored management to balance short-term protection with long-term sustainability. Zone 1 demands urgent left bank protection (revetments, groynes, embankments) alongside long-term measures such as riparian vegetation and buffer zones, while right bank erosion and accretion call for protective works and dredging. Zone 2’s mixed behavior requires artificial protection in unstable left and right bank sectors, with continuous monitoring of accreting reaches. Zone 3’s severe left bank retreat necessitates immediate intervention, while stable or depositional right bank areas need selective dredging

to maintain navigability. Zone 4, one of the most critical stretches, requires strong protective structures on the left bank and a combination of engineering, ecological management, and dredging on the right. Zone 5 calls for protective works in erosion-prone areas and careful monitoring or controlled dredging in depositional reaches. A zone specific, adaptive strategy is essential for sustainable management of the Brahmaputra floodplain.

4. Conclusion

This study highlights the Brahmaputra’s dynamic nature through hierarchical stream classification, spatio-temporal bankline analysis, and predictive modeling. Findings emphasize the need for zone-specific interventions that integrate engineering solutions with ecological restoration and community participation. The approach demonstrates how geospatial tools can support sustainable river management and inform policy decisions in Bangladesh’s most critical fluvial system.

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Evaluating Traffic-Related Air Pollution and Mitigation Through Optimal Air Purifier Placement in Khulna City

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Keywords

Air pollution, GIS suitability analysis, traffic emissions, Khulna City, air purifier placement

1. Introduction

In Khulna City, a fast-developing port and industrial city in the southwest part of Bangladesh, there are rising levels of PM_{2.5}, CO, NO₂, SO₂, and HCHO as a result of heavy traffic, particularly in the commercial and industrial pathways (Saju et al., 2023). This paper will examine the correlation between vehicle size and concentration of air pollutants and determine the ideal places to install air cleaners in Khulna City. (Saju et al., 2023).

2. Materials and Methods

I. Study Area

This study focuses on the Khulna City Corporation (KCC) of the Khulna division, located in southwestern Bangladesh (22.8129° N, 89.5663° E), covering an area of 45.65 km² with an estimated population of 718,735. A total of 48 major road intersections were selected to evaluate the impact of vehicular activity on urban air pollution within the city.

II. Method:

This research integrates statistical analysis with GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) to evaluate traffic-related air pollution and identify suitable locations for air purifier installation. Satellite-derived air quality data for CO, NO₂, SO₂, PM_{2.5}, and HCHO were obtained from Sentinel-5P (TROPOMI) via the Google Earth Engine (GEE) JavaScript API for the year 2023, using monthly averaged concentrations. Vehicular volume data were collected through field surveys at 48 key intersections during 2023 and aggregated as monthly averages before being geocoded for spatial analysis. The correlation and the linear regression techniques were employed by Pearson to test the correlation between the volume of the vehicles (X) and the concentration of the pollutants (Y) based on the equation: $Y = a + bX$ in which a and b are the intercept and slope respectively. These analyses were applied to

estimate the relationships between traffic and pollution, and also to justify the choice and weight of the influencing factors, but regression coefficients and intercept values were not applied directly in spatial weighting. The conversion of all the vectors to raster format was performed with a cell size of 10m. The proximity-based features analysis employed the Euclidean Distance method and re-classified all the criteria layers to seven ordinal ranks (1-7) (Alshuwai-khat et al., 2024). It was assumed that each selected air pollutant contributes equally to the overall gas pollution burden due to the lack of locally specific weighting coefficients. The standardized pollutant raster was then averaged to create a so-called composite Air Quality Index (AQI):

$$GPI = \frac{NO_2 + PM_{2.5} + SO_2 + CO + HCHO}{5}$$

The final suitability score for each pixel was computed by:

$$S_{ij} = (PD_{ij} \times 0.25) + (I_{ij} \times 0.15) + (C_{ij} \times 0.10) + (R_{ij} \times 0.10) + (HT_{ij} \times 0.05) + (IN_{ij} \times 0.05) + (GAS_{ij} \times 0.30)$$

where S_{ij} denotes the overall suitability value at pixel (i,j). The resulting raster was normalized to a 1–10 scale to produce the final Air Purifier Suitability Map, identifying priority zones for installation across Khulna City.

3. Results and Discussion

The results reveal a distinct spatial pattern in the distribution of vehicular emissions and pollutant concentrations across Khulna City. Regression and correlation analyses between vehicle volume and major air pollutants show a moderately positive relationship, confirming that traffic intensity significantly influences local air quality. Among the pollutants, PM_{2.5} exhibited the strongest correlation ($r = 0.470$), followed by HCHO ($r = 0.473$), NO₂ ($r = 0.419$), SO₂ ($r = 0.425$), and CO ($r = 0.177$). These relationships indicate that although vehicular activity is a dominant emission source, other urban factors such as indus-

trial discharges and commercial activities also contribute to the overall pollution load. Spatial analysis using the GIS-based weighted overlay model identified three major clusters of high suitability for air purifier installation in Khulna City (Fig 2). The first cluster is concentrated in Daulatpur, particularly along Jessore Road, where dense traffic and nearby industries contribute to high pollutant accumulation.

Fig 1: Regression & Correlation of Air Pollutant with Vehicle Volume

Fig 2: Optimal air purifier suitability map

The second cluster extends across Khalishpur and Gowlapara (Wards 10–11), covering BIDC Road, Road No. 11, and Charerhat Main Road, characterized by mixed industrial and residential activity. The second cluster extends across Khalishpur and Gowlapara (Wards 10–11), covering BIDC Road, Road No. 11, and Charerhat Main Road, characterized by mixed indus-

trial and residential activity. The third cluster, encompassing Goborchaka, Sheikhpura, and Nirala, follows major corridors such as KDA Avenue, Khan Jahan Ali Road, Jabbar Sarani, and Sher-E-Bangla Road, dominated by commercial and institutional land uses with elevated exposure risk. The suitability map shows that high-suitability zones (≥ 5) are concentrated along major roads, intersections, and densely populated areas, where emission sources and human exposure overlap. In contrast, low-suitability zones (≤ 3) are found in peripheral, low-traffic areas with minimal industrial or commercial activity. These spatial patterns confirm that traffic volume and land-use intensity jointly influence air pollution in Khulna City. Installing air purifiers at key hotspots, particularly near schools, hospitals, and markets, can offer immediate benefits. Additionally, integrating solar-powered air purifiers with roadside tree plantations of high pollutant-absorbing species ensures both short-term filtration and long-term environmental improvement.

4. Conclusion

This paper has shown that the concentration of land-use and air pollution within the city is moderately dependent on traffic intensity and the level of land-use concentration of the Khulna City. The suitability analysis based on GIS was able to find the priority areas where air purifiers should be installed, which will facilitate the specific urban air quality responses. Nevertheless, equal pollutant weighting, satellite-based data, and under-sampling of traffic leads to an element of uncertainty which can be determined by future research methods that involve ground-level monitoring and health-based weighting plans.

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Assessing Accessibility to Green Spaces in Association with Mental Health of Urban Slum Dwellers in Khulna, Bangladesh

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Keywords

Canonical correlation analysis, Green space accessibility, Mental health, Urban slums.

1. Introduction

Rapid urbanization has intensified informal settlement growth where residents face overcrowding and limited recreational facilities, adversely impacting mental health. In Bangladesh, slum residents face barriers to green space access, contributing to stress and depression. Frequent nature contact benefits well-being, and perceived accessibility, including safety and inclusiveness, predicts green space use more reliably than proximity (White et al., 2021). This study uses canonical correlation analysis to examine whether better perceived access quality enhances green space use behavior and mental health, as measured by MHI-5, PSS-4, and WHO-5 among urban slum dwellers in Khulna, thereby contributing to more inclusive and sustainable urban planning.

2. Materials and Methods

I. Study Area

Data were collected from 665 respondents across 12 slum communities within Khulna City Corporation.

II. Method

Perceived accessibility included: (i) Perceived Access (km)—self-reported distance to nearest recreational facility; (ii) Safety—binary assessment (1=no concerns, 0=concerns present); (iii) Inclusiveness—ordinal scale evaluating accommodation of different age groups and abilities. Besides, use behavior measured via visit frequency (daily to rarely, ordinal) and visit duration (continuous hours). Mental health assessed via MHI-5 (emotional well-being), PSS-4 (perceived stress), and WHO-5 (positive well-being)

Green space use was assessed by how often and how long residents visited, while mental health was measured with MHI-5, PSS-4, and WHO-5 scales.

Fig 1 : Methodological Framework of the Study

Six canonical correlation models examined relationships between variable sets. CCA identifies linear combinations maximizing correlation (Hotelling, 1936):

$$r_k = \frac{\text{Cov}(U_k, V_k)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(U_k) \cdot \text{Var}(V_k)}} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where U and V represent canonical variates from predictor and outcome sets. Models are - Access & Quality → Use Behavior (1), Use Behavior → MHI-5 (2), Use Behavior → PSS-4 (3), Access Quality → MHI-5 (4), Access Quality → PSS-4 (5), Access Quality → WHO-5 (6). Listwise deletion yielded N=628 for use behavior models and N=665 for access-health models.

3. Results and Discussion

Fig 2 presents the conceptual framework illustrating pathways linking perceived access quality, use behavior, and mental health across all six models. Fig 3 and Fig 4 show different canonical variate’s structure.

Fig 2 : Conceptual Framework Diagram of canonical Correlation Models Construction

Model	Canonical Variates (U ₁ , V ₁)	Variable Name	Remark
Model 1	Perceived Access and Quality (U ₁)	Perceived Access (km)	N/A
		Inclusiveness	N/A
		Safety	N/A
Residents' Green Space Use Behavior (V ₁)	Residents' Green Space Use Behavior (U ₁)	Visit Frequency	N/A
		Visit Duration	N/A
Model 2	Residents' Mental Health (MHI-5)(V ₁)	mhi1	Been a nervous person
		mhi2	Calm and peaceful
		mhi3	Been a happy person
		mhi4	Been downhearted and depressed
		mhi5	Nothing could cheer you up
Model 3	Residents' Perceived Stress (PSS 4)(V ₁)	Visit Frequency	N/A
		Visit Duration	N/A
		pss1	Confidence
		pss2	Control difficulties
		pss3	Things going your way
		pss4	Difficulties piling up so high

Fig 3 : Canonical Variates Structure Models

Model	Canonical Variates (U ₁ , V ₁)	Variable Name	Remark
Model 4	Perceived Access and Quality (U ₁)	Perceived Access (km)	N/A
		Inclusiveness	N/A
		Safety	N/A
Residents' Mental Health (MHI-5)(V ₁)		mhi1	Been a nervous person
		mhi2	Calm and peaceful
		mhi3	Been a happy person
		mhi4	Been downhearted and depressed
		mhi5	Nothing could cheer you up
Model 5	Residents' Perceived Stress (PSS 4)(V ₁)	Perceived Access (km)	N/A
		Inclusiveness	N/A
		Safety	N/A
		pss1	Confidence
		pss2	Control difficulties
		pss3	Things going your way
		pss4	Difficulties piling up so high
Model 6	WHO-5 Well Being Index (V ₁)	Perceived Access (km)	N/A
		Inclusiveness	N/A
		Safety	N/A
		wh1	Relaxed
		wh2	Rested
		wh3	Active
		wh4	Cheerful
		wh5	Daily Life filled with things which interests

Fig 4 : Canonical Variates Structure Models

All models demonstrated significant associations ($p < 0.001$). Canonical correlations ranged from $r = 0.218$ to $r = 0.336$. Model 5 (Access Quality → Perceived Stress) showed strongest relationship ($r = 0.336$).

Perceived negatively correlated with visit frequency (coefficient = -0.408), which was strongly positively associated with better mental health (0.906), consistent with patterns found in other international studies (McCormack et al., 2007). Safety and inclusiveness contributed moderate positive effects (0.291 and 0.244). Visit frequency more strongly related to mental health outcomes (0.874 – 0.949) than visit duration (0.198 – 0.237), aligning with psychological research on the benefits of micro-dose nature contact (van den Berg et al., 2016). WHO-5 well-being showed strong positive associations with accessibility (0.954 – 0.960). These findings corroborate evidence that perceived

accessibility more accurately predicts green space use than objective proximity, emphasizing the need for urban planning to enhance accessibility, safety, and inclusiveness in vulnerable communities to support mental health.

Fig 5 : Standardized Coefficients Across Six Models

4. Conclusion

This study emphasizes integrating community health into urban development in informal settlements by improving perceived access to green spaces. It shows that mental health in slum residents is strongly linked to how often they visit green spaces, which depends on factors like proximity, safety, and inclusiveness. Aligning with SDG Goal 11, urban planning must ensure sustainable, equitable, and inclusive access to green spaces for marginalized populations to enhance overall community well-being.

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Evaluating the Spatial Transferability of Soil Salinity Prediction Models in the Southwestern Coastal Region of Bangladesh

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Keywords

Machine Learning, Remote Sensing, Soil Salinity, Spatial Transferability, Coastal Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Soil salinization threatens agricultural productivity and food security in coastal Bangladesh (SRDI, 2010; Rahman et al., 2017). Although remote sensing (RS) and machine learning (ML) are effective for predicting soil salinity, a key challenge is spatial transferability: the ability of a model trained in one area to maintain accuracy in another without retraining. In reality, models often lose performance when applied to neighbouring districts due to environmental differences (Brenning et al., 2015). This study develops soil salinity prediction models and evaluates their cross-district performance in southwestern coastal Bangladesh. To our knowledge, this is the first study in the region to quantify spatial transferability using Relative Performance Drop.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in three adjacent southwestern coastal districts of Bangladesh: Satkhira, Khulna, and Jessore. These districts represent a gradient of salinity severity, from the highly saline Satkhira (near the coast) to the moderately saline Jessore (further inland), providing an ideal laboratory for testing model transferability.

Fig 1: Study Area

2.2 Method

A comprehensive methodology integrated field data, satellite imagery, and geospatial analysis was used in this study.

2.2.1 Data Collection

A total of 162 topsoil samples collected during a field campaign in March 2024 across the study districts were used (Sarkar et al., 2024). Soil Electrical Conductivity (EC) was measured as ground truth, with values ranging from 0.05 to 9.09 mS/cm. Corresponding Landsat 8 imagery was processed via Google Earth Engine to compute 19 spectral indices (e.g., NDVI, SAVI, NDSI) (Douaoui et al., 2006; Khan et al., 2005).

2.2.2 Geospatial Factors

Key environmental covariates were integrated, including distance from the coastline, rivers, and the Sundarbans, as well as topographic indices (slope, aspect) derived from a DEM.

2.2.3 Machine Learning & Transferability Assessment

Predictor variables were standardized, and hyperparameters were tuned through grid search with cross-validation. Nine machine learning algorithms (Random Forest, SVR, XGBoost, etc.) were trained on two combined datasets and evaluated using within-domain and cross-domain validation. Spatial transferability was quantified using the Relative Performance Drop (RPD).

Fig 2: Methodological Framework of the Research

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Correlation Insights

Correlation analysis revealed that vegetation indices (NDVI, SAVI, EVI) had strong negative correlations

with salinity ($r = -0.5$ to -0.6), while salinity and brightness indices (NDSI, SI) showed positive correlations ($r = +0.4$ to $+0.6$). Among geospatial factors, distance from the coastline was the most significant predictor ($r = -0.39$ to -0.51), confirming a strong coastal-inland salinity gradient.

Fig 3: Correlation of Salinity and Predictor Variables

3.2 Model Performance and Transferability

The models performed well within their respective training domains. Among the nine algorithms tested, SVR achieved the highest internal accuracy ($R^2 \approx 0.54$, RMSE = 1.21 mS/cm, MAE = 0.94 mS/cm). However, a clear performance decline was observed during cross-district validation, indicating limitations in spatial transferability. The inclusion of geospatial factors improved model robustness and reduced the Relative Performance Drop (RPD) by up to 20 percentage points for algorithms such as Random Forest. Within this integrated framework, SVR exhibited the smallest transferability gap, confirming its reliability for cross-district soil salinity prediction.

Fig 4: Relative Performance Drop (RMSE) of Satkhira Khulna dataset

Fig 5: Relative Performance Drop (RMSE) of Satkhira Jessore dataset

Fig 6: Average Transferability Gap (R^2) of ML Models

4. Conclusion

This study confirms that machine learning models can effectively predict soil salinity; however, their generalization across regions is not guaranteed. Enhancing spatial transferability requires integrating stable geospatial factors, such as distance from the coastline, with spectral indices to produce more physio-graphically grounded predictions (Gorji et al., 2020). Although SVR emerged as the most transferable algorithm, variations in performance across district pairs highlight the importance of local environmental context. The findings provide a practical and scalable framework for regional-scale salinity monitoring, supporting sustainable land and water management under the Bangladesh Delta Plan 2100 and reducing reliance on repetitive and costly field surveys. Future research should incorporate larger multi-season datasets, explore deep learning approaches to improve model generalization, and integrate climate projections for long-term salinity risk assessment.

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Simulation-Based 2D Flood Modeling Through Application of HEC-RAS in Khulna City

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Keywords

Urban flooding, Hydrodynamic modeling, HEC-RAS 2D, Infiltration, Drainage network

1. Introduction

Khulna City Corporation (KCC), situated in the southwest coastal region of Bangladesh, experiences recurrent urban flooding triggered by intense rainfall, poor drainage, and unplanned urbanization (Sarkar et al., 2020). Low elevation and encroachment upon natural retention basins have amplified surface runoff, while the aging drainage system remains unable to manage stormwater during extreme events. Despite ongoing municipal interventions, flood modeling in Khulna largely depends on field observations or static drainage assessments lacking process-based analysis (Sultana, 2024). To address this gap, this study employs a high-resolution two-dimensional hydrodynamic model using HEC-RAS 6.7 Beta-4a to simulate rainfall-driven flood inundation in four of the most flood-prone wards: 27, 28, 30, and 31. The objectives include quantifying inundation depth and extent under multiple rainfall return periods, evaluating the drainage system's performance, and assessing the exposure of the urban road network to flooding.

2. Materials and Methods

The HEC-RAS 2D diffusion-wave solver was applied under a "rain-on-grid" configuration to simulate surface flow dynamics across the four selected wards. A high-precision 1-meter Digital Elevation Model (DEM) was developed by integrating spot height data, building structures, and water bodies, ensuring accurate terrain representation. The DEM was converted into a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) within RAS Mapper, from which a 5m × 5m computational mesh (258,103 cells) was generated to balance spatial accuracy and computational efficiency. An infiltration layer was prepared using a Curve Number (CN) based approach that integrates Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) and hydrologic soil group data. The LULC map, derived from Sentinel-2 imagery, classified the area into built-up, vegetation, water body, and barren land categories, while soil data from USGS defined infiltration variability. The derived CN-based infiltration map

was then incorporated into HEC-RAS to simulate rainfall losses and runoff generation. Historical daily rainfall data (1948–2019) were analyzed to determine rainfall intensities for 2-, 5-, 10-, 25-, 50-, 75-, and 100- year return periods, estimated using the Hazen plotting position method. Corresponding rainfall depths (132–372 mm) served as model inputs. The stormwater drainage system, consisting of 1,168 nodes and 1,160 conduits, was integrated into the model using HEC-RAS's experimental drainage network feature to replicate surface–subsurface interactions. Boundary conditions were assigned as normal depth outflows to allow realistic drainage discharge. Model stability was ensured through Courant-based time-step control (1-second computation interval) and mass balance monitoring. Validation was conducted using field observations and photographic evidence of real flood events to verify spatial agreement between simulated and observed inundation patterns.

3. Results and Discussion

According to Fig 1 & Fig 2, the model simulations show that even under a relatively moderate 2-year return period, nearly 52% of the study area becomes inundated, indicating that Khulna's existing stormwater system is already functioning close to its capacity. As rainfall intensity increases, the inundation extent expands steadily, reaching around 65% under the 100-year return period. In Fig 2 we can see that Flood depths frequently exceed 30 cm in central and southern low-lying zones such as Tootpara, Labanchora, and Jaikhana Mor, where dense built-up areas and clayey soils restrict infiltration and accelerate surface runoff accumulation. According to figure 3, The road network analysis revealed that about 54% of total road length, especially semi-pucca and kutcha roads, becomes inundated under extreme rainfall conditions, while pucca roads remain relatively less affected due to better drainage and elevation. Such widespread road flooding disrupts mobility, hampers emergency response, and causes economic and infrastructural challenges, highlighting the urgent need for flood-resilient urban transport planning. Figure 4 illustrates model validation using field observations and photographic evidence confirmed a strong spatial match between simulated and observed inundation patterns, verifying

the accuracy and reliability of the hydrodynamic setup. The model effectively captured flood-prone zones and drainage bottlenecks, aligning with earlier studies in similar coastal cities that link increased flooding to rapid urbanization and inadequate stormwater management. Overall, the findings demonstrate that uncontrolled land-use change and the loss of natural retention areas have significantly reduced infiltration capacity, amplifying runoff and flood severity. To address these challenges, the study recommends drainage rehabilitation, wetland restoration, and the integration of flood-resilient design within future urban development plans to strengthen Khulna’s adaptive capacity and long-term urban resilience.

Fig 4: Model Validation

4. Conclusion

This research demonstrates the application of a high-resolution HEC-RAS 2D hydrodynamic framework for modeling urban flood dynamics in Khulna City Corporation. The integrated approach combining topographic, land-use, soil, and rainfall data successfully reproduced realistic inundation patterns validated through field evidence. Findings reveal that Khulna’s existing drainage system is inadequate to manage rainfall beyond short return periods, with over half of the study area inundated even during minor storm events. The study provides a replicable, cost-effective modeling methodology suitable for medium-sized cities in developing regions. By quantifying flood risk and infrastructure vulnerability, it supports evidence-based urban planning and climate-resilient drainage design. Strengthening stormwater management, restoring natural detention areas, and adopting adaptive infrastructure planning are critical to enhancing Khulna’s long-term urban resilience.

Fig 1: Inundation Map of 2 Years, 5 Years, 10 Years, 25 Years, 50 Years & 100 Years Return Periods

Fig 2: Under Different Return Periods

Fig 3: Impact on Road Networks

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Harnessing Remote Sensing and Machine Learning to Map Drought Severity in Bangladesh

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Keywords

Drought, Remote Sensing, Machine Learning, CatBoost, Climate Resilience, Bangladesh

1. Introduction

This study combines multisource remote sensing indices with ensemble machine learning in order to quantify, classify, and spatialize the temporal trend of drought severity during 2017-2024 in Bangladesh. It seeks to determine the most significant environmental drivers for drought severity, assess the predictive power of the CatBoost algorithm, and generate an integrated drought risk map to inform adaptive planning and water resource management.

2. Materials and Methods

The research covers the entire Bangladesh region ($\approx 147,570 \text{ km}^2$), a South Asian delta low-lying and surrounded by India, Myanmar, and the Bay of Bengal. The substantial portion of land is cultivable alluvial plains constructed through the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna River system. Monsoon-induced rainfall is around 2,500 mm per year but is highly spatial and temporal in variability, and frequent droughts are particularly prevalent in Bangladesh (Chowdhury et al., 2019; Sarkar et al., 2024).

Fig 1: Map of Study Area

A total of ten remote sensing drought indicators—ETCI, NDMI, NDVI, NDWI, NMDI, PCI, SMCI, TCI, VCI, and VHI—were derived from Sentinel-2, MODIS, Landsat-8, CHIRPS, and NASA datasets. Each index

was harmonized to a 30 m spatial resolution using Google Earth Engine (GEE) and reclassified into five drought severity classes through the Reclassify tool in ArcGIS Pro. Cloud masking using QA bands was applied, and all datasets were resampled and normalized to ensure consistency before classification. SPI and SPEI indices, computed from CHIRPS rainfall data, were used as reference variables to represent short- and long-term drought conditions (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010). The CatBoost gradient boosting model was employed to determine the relative influence of each drought indicator. CatBoost was selected over Random Forest and XGBoost due to its superior ability to handle multicollinearity and complex nonlinear interactions among highly correlated climatic and vegetation variables, while reducing overfitting bias (Prokhorenkova et al., 2018). The dataset was split into 70% training and 30% testing portions, and model validation was performed using RMSE, MAE, R^2 , and F1-score metrics. Hyperparameter tuning optimized model depth, learning rate, and iterations to minimize prediction errors and prevent overfitting. The final influence scores from the model were integrated into GIS-based weighted overlay analysis to produce annual drought severity maps from 2017 to 2024.

Fig 2: Graphical Presentation of Method

3. Results and Discussion

The CatBoost model performed strong predictive accuracy across all the validation measures, $R^2 > 0.88$, $F1 > 0.80$, and $RMSE < 0.20$, confirming high accuracy in drought classification. Vegetation- and moisture-related indices (VHI, NDVI, NDMI, and VCI) contributed

the most to drought prediction, followed by precipitation- and evapotranspiration-induced indices (PCI, ETCI, and TCI). Of all the variables, the Vegetation Health Index (VHI) contributed the most at approximately 10.9% to the overall drought model. Other major contributing indices included NDVI & VCI (10.3%), NDMI (10.2%), and PCI (10%), indicating the dominant role of vegetation and moisture dynamics in drought prediction. Geographically, the results reflected a clear north-south divide: the northwestern regions (Rajshahi, Rangpur, Bogura) experienced repeated and intense droughts, while the southern and southeastern regions (Khulna, Barishal, Chattogram) showed relatively higher hydrological and vegetation statuses. SPI and SPEI maps both showed the continuity of drought in the northwestern areas

Fig 3: Drought distribution map showing north-south gradient (2017-2024)

and some climatic recovery in 2023-2024, with increasing low-severity drought regions suggesting the stability of ecosystems over time.

Year	Accuracy Type	SPI 3	SPI 6	SPI 9	SPI 12	SPEI 3	SPEI 6	SPEI 9	SPEI 12
2017	RMSE	0.2762	0.2665	0.1971	0.1612	0.1068	0.1132	0.1465	0.1247
	R ² Score	0.9128	0.9110	0.0907	0.8851	0.9082	0.9060	0.8996	0.8853
	MAE	0.2204	0.2083	0.1476	0.1027	0.0766	0.0870	0.1060	0.0808
	F1	0.7636	0.8943	0.9457	0.9457	0.9697	0.8760	0.8943	0.9697
2018	RMSE	0.1462	0.2063	0.1572	0.1407	0.1023	0.1255	0.1382	0.1247
	R ² Score	0.9085	0.9127	0.9061	0.9066	0.9094	0.9099	0.9046	0.9035
	MAE	0.1141	0.1664	0.1162	0.1056	0.0783	0.0964	0.0985	0.0931
	F1	0.8872	0.8346	0.8160	0.6667	0.8788	0.7967	0.7869	0.6545
2019	RMSE	0.1993	0.1022	0.0978	0.1150	0.1210	0.1025	0.1040	0.1185
	R ² Score	0.9102	0.8958	0.8932	0.9028	0.8737	0.8907	0.9011	0.8953
	MAE	0.1562	0.0740	0.0684	0.0843	0.0726	0.0681	0.0754	0.0850
	F1	0.6947	0.8411	0.8929	0.8077	0.8302	0.9027	0.8727	0.8519
2020	RMSE	0.2346	0.1380	0.1703	0.1341	0.1807	0.2229	0.1708	0.1969
	R ² Score	0.9138	0.9026	0.9061	0.9028	0.9074	0.9164	0.8975	0.9157
	MAE	0.1866	0.0950	0.1230	0.0937	0.1319	0.1762	0.1117	0.1498
	F1	0.9106	0.9365	0.8739	0.9365	0.7928	0.6990	0.8445	0.9194
2021	RMSE	0.1470	0.2180	0.1970	0.4689	0.1278	0.0931	0.2387	0.2239
	R ² Score	0.8910	0.9104	0.8908	0.8929	0.8995	0.8897	0.8980	0.8992
	MAE	0.0849	0.1711	0.1279	0.1119	0.0881	0.0598	0.1607	0.1627
	F1	0.9841	0.7573	0.9153	0.9921	0.8364	0.8772	0.8772	0.9841
2022	RMSE	0.2052	0.2798	0.1822	0.2099	0.1812	0.2365	0.1453	0.1844
	R ² Score	0.9008	0.8890	0.8968	0.9020	0.9059	0.9039	0.8892	0.9081
	MAE	0.1598	0.1814	0.1242	0.1515	0.1355	0.1635	0.0980	0.1458
	F1	0.9008	0.9333	0.8837	0.8197	0.9173	0.9333	0.8000	0.7797
2023	RMSE	0.1632	0.2629	0.1087	0.1606	0.1287	0.1829	0.1132	0.2252
	R ² Score	0.8854	0.8988	0.8910	0.8909	0.9013	0.9037	0.8862	0.8837
	MAE	0.1078	0.1911	0.0761	0.1054	0.0903	0.1210	0.0777	0.1382
	F1	0.9091	0.8750	0.9008	0.9333	0.7899	0.7797	0.9008	0.9333
2024	RMSE	0.2203	0.1703	0.1288	0.1105	0.1107	0.1226	0.0902	0.1034
	R ² Score	0.9102	0.9046	0.9103	0.8958	0.9046	0.8984	0.9047	0.9046
	MAE	0.1749	0.1253	0.0997	0.0758	0.0729	0.0790	0.0681	0.0778
	F1	0.8983	0.8983	0.8983	0.8496	0.7850	0.7850	0.8983	0.7850

Fig 4: Accuracy assessment of the model (RMSE, R², MAE and F1)

The Temporal trend revealed that the years 2019-2021 experienced the highest widespread drought stress, followed by moderate improvement in the years 2022-2024, which is in accordance with national climatic trends of monsoon variation. The results confirm the effectiveness of CatBoost in capturing fine-scale drought variability across Bangladesh.

4. Conclusion

This study successfully integrates remote sensing and machine learning techniques to map and predict drought severity across Bangladesh. The developed CatBoost model offers a reliable, data-driven framework that accurately captures spatial drought dynamics and identifies critical vulnerable zones. The outcomes highlight vegetation health, moisture stress, and precipitation anomalies as key determinants of drought conditions.

The results can guide agricultural zoning, irrigation prioritization, and water allocation strategies under the Bangladesh Delta Plan 2100. Furthermore, the developed framework can strengthen national drought early-warning systems and support climate-resilient land and water resource planning in Bangladesh.

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Assessing the Temporal Dynamics of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in Khulna City with Meteorological and Trajectory-based Analysis

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Keywords

NOAA Hy-Split trajectory model, particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), particulate matter (PM₁₀), seasonal-trend decomposition.

1. Introduction

Air pollution is a significant environmental problem in Bangladesh, where levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ often exceed WHO guideline values. Most studies focus on Dhaka, but Khulna City has not been studied as much, even though it is experiencing rapid industrial growth, urbanization, and is near coastal and cross-border pollution areas. Khulna is a key industrial center in southwestern Bangladesh, known for its shipyards, brick kilns, and export processing zones. It is becoming a hotspot for air pollution, but systematic assessments are lacking (Borchers-Arriagada et al., 2024).

This study aims to explore the changes in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations over time in Khulna City. It will use meteorological data and the NOAA-HYSPLIT trajectory model to understand both local weather effects and long-range transport of pollution (Al-Muyeed, 2016).

The main goals are to examine seasonal changes, evaluate how weather conditions affect particulate levels, and identify possible long-distance transport routes. The results will help develop urban air quality management strategies that respond to climate challenges and improve regional efforts to reduce air pollution in southern Bangladesh (Dihan et al., 2021).

2. Materials and Methods

Ground-level PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations, along with weather data (temperature, humidity, wind speed, solar radiation, precipitation, and barometric pressure), were collected from the DoE CAMS-8 station in Khulna for 2024. Wind trajectory data from the NOAA Hy-Split Model were extracted to examine air mass movements.

Data were processed and analyzed using Python (v3.10) and IBM SPSS Statistics (v29). We looked at changes over time during different parts of the day

(morning, afternoon, evening, night) and through the seasons (winter, spring, summer, monsoon, autumn). Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) models were used to assess how meteorological variables affect PM concentrations. MLR was chosen because it is simple, easy to interpret, and can measure the individual impact of each predictor variable. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was used to identify and address multicollinearity among predictors.

The NOAA-HYSPLIT model conducted backward trajectory analysis to trace where pollutants came from. K-means clustering sorted pollution intensity levels (Riches et al., 2022). STL (Seasonal-Trend Decomposition using LOESS) distinguished long-term trends from seasonal changes and leftover variations to reflect time-based dynamics (Borchers-Arriagada et al., 2024; Sreenivasulu & Rayalu, 2024). This study relies on a single monitoring station and one year of data. This limits the ability to generalize findings to different locations and times.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Average concentration of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀

Fig 1. Diurnal and Seasonal variation of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations in Khulna (2024)

Fig 1 shows the daily and seasonal changes of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in Khulna. Concentrations were highest at night due to stable atmospheric conditions. The levels peaked in winter, with PM_{2.5} reaching 132 µg/m³ and PM₁₀ at 206 µg/m³. This was due to limited dispersion and strong N/NW continental winds from northern Bangladesh and the Indo-Gangetic Plain. In contrast, monsoon levels were at their lowest, with PM_{2.5} at 21

$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and PM_{10} at $59 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The lower levels resulted from rainfall, improved dispersion, and cleaner S/SW maritime winds from the Bay of Bengal.

3.2. NOAA Hy-Split model extraction

As shown in Figure 2, NOAA-HYSPLIT results revealed that continental trajectories (42%) from the north/northwest mainly caused winter pollution. Ma-

Variable	$\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (β)	PM_{10} (β)	Effect Direction
Temperature	-1.029*	-0.590*	Strong Negative
Humidity	-0.676*	-0.621	Negative
Barometric Pressure	0.404*	0.431*	Positive
Wind Trajectory Height	0.253*	0.239*	Positive
Precipitation	-0.375	-0.621	Negative
Wind Speed	0.276*	0.122	Mixed Seasonal
Constant (Model R^2)	0.761-0.912	0.788-0.910	

* Significant at 95% confidence ($p < 0.05$)

rine inflows (33%) from the Bay of Bengal helped lower pollution levels in the monsoon.

Fig 2. NOAA-HYSPLIT Wind Trajectory

3.3. NOAA Hy-Split model extraction

Table 1. Best Seasonal Variation of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}

From Table 1 Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) showed that weather factors had a significant impact on particulate levels. The R^2 values were 0.556 for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and 0.497 for PM_{10} . For $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, temperature ($\beta = -0.507, p < 0.01$) and humidity ($\beta = -0.369, p < 0.05$) had the strongest negative effects. Pressure ($\beta = 0.356, p < 0.05$) and trajectory height ($\beta = 0.253, p < 0.05$) were positively correlated. The VIF value was less than 5, which confirmed no multicollinearity. Correlation heatmaps showed a strong relationship between PM and weather in winter ($r = 0.68$) and the weakest relationship in the monsoon ($r = 0.32$).

3.4. K-means cluster analysis

Fig 3. Boxplots of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} by cluster (0= Lower, 3=Very High)

Fig 3 shows K-means clustering ($k=4$) categorized $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ into four intensity levels: very low ($<40 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), moderate ($40-60 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), high ($60-90 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), and very high ($>90 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Mostly Northwestern wind was responsible for the very high pollution, and the Southern wind was responsible for the lower pollution.

3.5. Seasonal-Trend Decomposition

In Figure 4 STL decomposition indicated a seasonal amplitude of $22-27 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and a rising long-term trend of $+0.35 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3/\text{month}$, showing ongoing accumulation. In summary, temperature, humidity, and air mass trajectories

were the main factors affecting PM variation.

Fig 4. NOAA-HYSPLIT Wind Trajectory

Conclusion

This study shows diurnal and seasonal variability of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} levels in Khulna city, peaking at night and in winter due to poor dispersion and dominant N/NW continental transport, while monsoon reductions reflect maritime airflow and rainfall effects. Temperature, humidity, and air mass pathways significantly regulate particulate dynamics. Gradual upward trend is also visualized. The findings underline the need for winter-focused emission control system, expansion of monitoring station, and integration of trajectory-based forecasting into air quality management. The study provides a foundation for climate-responsive planning and regional cooperation to address transboundary pollution in southern Bangladesh.

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Robustness of delineating Tidal flats and Floodplains by using seasonal water extent imagery

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Keywords

Binary classification, Intertidal zone, Jamuna River, Meghna Delta, Robustness score.

1. Introduction

This study finds out the dynamics of tidal flats in the Meghna Delta and floodplains in the Jamuna River system by applying a seasonal water extent-based delineation approach. These intertidal zones face a dynamic situation due to flood, tide cycle and cyclone. The overall aim of this study is to delineate tidal flats and floodplains in Meghna delta and Jamuna river and identify the spatio-temporal variability during 1990 to 2023. The study can be a rapid, cost-effective delineation method for different landscape types, providing broad insight of water extent and land cover dynamics over decades.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

Tidal flat and permanent land areas were quantified for both the Meghna Delta and the Jamuna River course, including their surrounding landscapes.

Fig 1. Map of Study Area

2.2. Method

Satellite imagery collected from Landsat 5, Landsat 8, and Sentinel-2A, was processed through the Google Earth Engine (GEE) JavaScript API from 1990 to 2023 at five-year intervals, from which the Normalized Dif-

ference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) were derived. NDWI used to indicate as maximum water extents; NDVI was used to delineate minimum extents (Jia et al., 2021). Then NDVI and NDWI images were binary classified by using the Natural Breaks method to distinguish land and water. Subtracting NDWI from NDVI isolated the tidal flat areas. This produced three categories—land, water, and tidal flats (Chang et al., 2022; Jia et al., 2021). Hotspot is delineated by using the image analyst's difference function in ArcGIS Pro, generating raster layers that captured positive and negative tidal flat changes across time intervals. These results were further combined using raster calculator or "combined" tool to create cumulative hotspot maps of significant tidal flat dynamics.

Accuracy was assessed using 30 random validation points per year across three land classes (permanent land, tidal flat, and water), with confusion matrices generated from classified outputs and Google Earth Pro imagery. Reliability was measured using Kappa Coefficient along with Overall, Producer's, and User's Accuracy (Rwanga & Ndambuki, 2017). Tidal flat dynamics were quantified through percentage rate of change, where higher values indicated more significant intertidal shifts.

Methodological robustness was evaluated using a composite score that integrated Kappa, overall accuracy, analysis accuracy, and ground data accuracy, normalized on a 0–1 scale and weighted, with the Kappa Coefficient receiving the highest weight in classification reliability. Equation (Error! Reference source not found.) adopted from (Y. Chen, 2021) where W_1, W_2, W_3, W_4 are the assigned weighted value for each criterion.

$$\text{Robustness Score} = (W_1 \times \text{Kappa Coefficient}) + (W_2 \times \text{Overall Accuracy}) + (W_3 \times \text{Analysis Accuracy}) + (W_4 \times \text{Ground Data Accuracy}) \quad (1)$$

3. Results and Discussion

The results show seasonality in terms of tidal flat and permanent land formation. It also shows that, permanent land has generally expanded in both study areas over the last three decades. In the Meghna Delta, permanent

land increased at a rate of 6.62%, whereas the Jamuna River floodplain exhibited a much higher rate of change, with tidal flat and floodplain formation expanding by 27.15%.

Fig 2. Time Series Representation of Tidal flats and Floodplains

These findings highlight that while both systems are dynamic, but Jamuna River faces more impact because of seasonal water extent, as Meghna Delta has less influence on seasonal water extent.

Fig 4. Area of Tidal flat and Permanent land in Meghna Delta and Jamuna River

Furthermore, the central part of Meghna Delta and moreover the whole river course of Jamuna River faces most dynamic change in the study time period.

Fig 5. Most Changed Places at Meghna Delta and Jamuna River

Accuracy assessment was calculated by using the Kappa coefficient method. The average Kappa values were 88.65% for the Meghna Delta and 92.81% for the Jamuna River, shows high reliability of the classification results. Furthermore, a robustness score was calculated by incorporating weighted accuracy metrics.

The result shows that the Jamuna River showed a ro-

bustness score 3.5% higher than the Meghna Delta, indicating greater consistency of the method in this region.

4. Conclusion

The study assesses the tidal flat land and permanent land area in the Meghna Delta and Jamuna River course including its surrounding. These results provide knowledge for river management, disaster preparedness, and long-term planning under the Bangladesh Delta Plan 2100 (BDP 2100). The study highlights the influence of floods, cyclones, and seasonal variability in shaping long-term land-water dynamics. These findings are directly related for river management, disaster risk reduction, and the design of adaptive strategies under the BDP 2100. By linking the study with planning needs, the study provides a practical framework for policymakers, environmental planners, and local communities seeking sustainable methods to manage the dynamic deltaic and riverine systems of Bangladesh.

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Optimized Geohazard Monitoring Using DInSAR, InSAR and Machine Learning Algorithms in Deltaic Bangladesh

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Keywords

SAR, Remote Sensing, Data-driven Modelling, Land Management

1. Introduction

Land subsidence is a major geohazard in deltaic cities caused by over-extraction of groundwater, urbanization, and geological compaction. Khulna City Corporation (KCC) faces increasing subsidence risks due to infrastructure loading and aquifer depletion. This study integrates Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (DInSAR), Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR), and ensemble machine learning models to assess and predict subsidence from 2016 to 2024. At present, prediction of environmental hazards are now employed by machine learning algorithms performed very well in recent years [1] [2].

2. Materials and Methods

The study area covers KCC, a deltaic urban region in southwestern Bangladesh spanning about 45.65 km². Bounded by the Rupsha and Bhairab rivers, it lies within the Ganges–Brahmaputra Delta, characterized by soft Holocene sediments, low elevation (1–4 m), and intense urban development, making it highly susceptible to land subsidence and tidal impacts.

Fig 1: Map of the Study Area

Sentinel-1A SAR datasets from 2016 to 2024 were processed using the DInSAR and InSAR techniques within the ESA SNAP software to quantify land subsidence across KCC. Precise orbit files, radiometric calibration, and coregistration were applied to generate interferograms, followed by Goldstein phase filtering and phase unwrapping via SNAPHU to derive line-of-sight displacement maps. Vertical subsidence rates were calculated and geocoded into WGS 1984 using Range Doppler Terrain Correction.

To identify the driving factors of subsidence, twelve environmental and geological parameters DEM, slope, rainfall, soil type, GWL, NDVI, NDBI, LULC, permeability, and distances to river, road, and fault were integrated and analyzed [3] [4]. An ensemble machine learning framework comprising Random Forest, XGBoost, CatBoost, and GBDT was developed in Python, trained on 70% of samples and validated on 30%. Model performance was evaluated using R², RMSE, and MAE, while SHAP analysis was used to interpret variable influence and explain model predictions.

Fig 2: Methodology framework of DInSAR, InSAR and land subsidence prediction

3. Results and Discussion

The present study offers a nine-year temporal analysis of land subsidence utilizing DInSAR, revealing distinct spatial and temporal variations in deformation across Khulna City Corporation (KCC) between 2016 and 2024. The DInSAR-derived results indicate that annual

subsidence rates fluctuated between -0.93 mm/year in 2016 and -5.88 mm/year in 2021, marking 2020–2021 as the most critical period of ground sinking. Areas dominated by industrial expansion and dense built-up land exhibited the highest deformation, while vegetated and open zones remained relatively stable, reflecting the influence of urban loading and groundwater withdrawal on land compaction [5]. The InSAR-based cumulative assessment further substantiated these findings, estimating long-term deformation rates of up to -5.16 mm/year across the study area. Spatial distribution maps derived from InSAR revealed a consistent subsidence pattern concentrated in the southern and central portions of KCC, aligning with regions of intense infrastructural development and shallow aquifer depletion. The temporal coherence between DInSAR and InSAR results confirmed the robustness of interferometric SAR techniques for long-term geohazard monitoring in deltaic environments [6].

Integrating Multi-Hazard, Exposure, and Adaptive Capacity Indicators for Urban Vulnerability Mapping in Dhaka Using Remote Sensing and GIS

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Keywords

Composite Vulnerability Index, geographic information system, multi-hazard assessment, urban resilience.

1. Introduction

Dhaka, one of the world's fastest-growing megacities, faces increasing risks from flooding, heat stress, air pollution, and seismic hazards (Rana et al., 2022). Rapid land-use change, high population density, and inadequate infrastructure have intensified these challenges (Dewan et al., 2012; Islam et al., 2020), underscoring the need for effective urban vulnerability mapping. While many studies focus on individual hazards, fewer integrate multiple hazards with exposure and adaptive capacity within a single planning framework. This study is novel in developing an integrated Composite Vulnerability Index (CVI) that combines multi-hazard, exposure, and adaptive capacity indicators to support metropolitan-scale resilience planning in Dhaka. Using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Saaty, 2008) and remote sensing-GIS techniques, spatial vulnerability patterns are assessed across the Dhaka Metropolitan Development Plan (DMDP) area for 2024. The study aims to:

1. Map the spatial distribution of major urban hazards;
2. Develop a CVI integrating hazard, exposure, and adaptive capacity indicators; and
3. Identify high-risk zones and analyze relationships between influencing factors and the CVI to support resilience planning.

2. Materials and Methods

The study area covers the Dhaka Metropolitan Development Plan (DMDP) region ($\approx 1,530 \text{ km}^2$), including Dhaka North and South City Corporations, Narayanganj, Gazipur, and surrounding upazilas (RAJUK, 1995). Thirteen indicators were used to develop the Composite Vulnerability Index (CVI), grouped into hazard, exposure, and adaptive capacity. Hazard indicators include flood risk, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration, pollut-

ing sources, daytime and nighttime land surface temperature (LST), and earthquake hazard. Exposure is represented by population density, built-up density, and critical facilities such as major transportation infrastructure. Adaptive capacity include health facilities, emergency services, green space, and water bodies. Indicator selection followed a systematic screening approach to ensure transparency and robustness, based on relevance to the vulnerability framework, ability to reflect Dhaka's main risks, support in existing studies, and availability of reliable spatial data. The DMDP area was chosen for its rapid urbanization, high population density, diverse hazard exposure, and its role as the statutory planning boundary of Dhaka. All datasets were projected to a common coordinate system, resampled to 100 m resolution, and normalized to a 0–1 scale. Indicator weights were derived using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) with acceptable consistency ($\text{CR} < 0.1$) (Saaty, 1977), and aggregated to compute the CVI

($\text{CVI} = \text{Hazard} + \text{Exposure} - \text{Adaptive Capacity}$).

The resulting CVI raster was classified into five vulnerability levels using the Natural Breaks method and validated through Spearman's rank correlation to examine relationships between CVI and influencing factors.

3. Results and Discussion

The spatial analysis of the Composite Vulnerability Index (CVI) revealed marked heterogeneity across the Dhaka Metropolitan Development Plan (DMDP) region. Central city corporations including Dhaka North (0.214), Dhaka South (0.231), and Narayanganj (0.218), exhibited very high vulnerability, despite relatively higher adaptive capacity in some areas. Adjacent upazilas like Rupganj (0.129) showed high vulnerability, while moderate zones included Savar (0.088), Gazipur City Corporation (0.092), Gazipur Sadar (0.097), Narayanganj Sadar (0.100), and Kaliganj (0.109), reflecting growing urban activities and mixed land use. Peripheral areas such as Keraniganj (0.076), Sonargaon (0.067), and Bandar (0.051) exhibited low to very low vulnerability, benefiting from greater environmental buffering and lower population exposure.

Fig 1. Composite Vulnerability Map

Table 1. Mean CVI and vulnerability level by administrative zone

Administrative Unit	Mean CVI	Vulnerability Level
Bandar Upazila	0.051	Very Low
Sonargaon Upazila	0.0667	Low
Keraniganj Upazila	0.0757	Low
Savar Upazila	0.0881	Moderate
Gazipur City Corporation	0.0917	Moderate
Gazipur Sadar Upazila	0.0971	Moderate
Narayanganj Sadar Upazila	0.0997	Moderate
Kaliganj Upazila	0.1089	Moderate
Rupganj Upazila	0.1290	High
Dhaka North City Corporation	0.2141	Very High
Narayanganj City Corporation	0.2179	Very High
Dhaka South City Corporation	0.2314	Very High

The Spearman’s rank correlation analysis shows that built-up area ($r = 0.636$), daytime LST ($r = 0.615$), and waterbody coverage ($r = 0.657$) have strong positive correlations with CVI ($p < 0.05$), indicating that urban density and thermal conditions are key drivers of vulnerability. Moderate correlations with nighttime LST, air pollution, flood, and population density suggest additional but less dominant influences. In contrast, earthquake proximity, polluting sources, critical facilities, and emergency or medical services show weak or negative associations, implying limited direct impact within the current spatial configuration. Overall,

Dhaka South, Dhaka North, and Narayanganj are the most vulnerable due to rapid, unmanaged urban growth, dense built-up areas, loss of green space, and rising heat and air pollution. Despite better infrastructure, unchecked development has exceeded environmental limits, increasing heat stress, flood risk, and hazards. Peripheral upazilas like Keraniganj, Sonargaon, and Bandar are less vulnerable due to lower development and natural buffers. The findings highlight the need for stricter land-use regulation, protection of water bodies, and expanded green infrastructure in core urban areas.

4. Conclusion

Dhaka’s central areas including Dhaka North, Dhaka South, and Narayanganj City, exhibit the highest composite vulnerability due to rapid urbanization, heat stress, and air pollution, while peripheral zones remain more resilient. The study highlights the urgent need for integrating green infrastructure, land-use control, and heat mitigation strategies into Dhaka’s future urban planning to build climate-resilient cities.

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A Computer Vision and Simulation Framework for LOS Assessment in Major Intersections of Khulna

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Keywords

YOLO, IOU, Computer Vision, Object Detection, Precision, Recall, mAP, PCU, Vissim, Traffic Simulation, on peak, off peak, Level of Service (LOS).

1. Introduction

This study investigates the performance and Level of Service (LOS) of major intersections in Khulna City through the integration of autonomous vehicle detection and traffic simulation. This study is significant because rapid urban growth, increasing traffic demand, and heterogeneous vehicle composition in Khulna have intensified intersection congestion, making a data-driven assessment of Level of Service (LOS) essential for effective traffic management (Noor et al., 2021). The assessment utilizes real-time video footage processed using the YOLOv11n deep learning model to identify and classify heterogeneous vehicle types under mixed traffic conditions. Detected traffic data were analyzed and simulated in Vissim to evaluate intersection performance during both peak and off-peak hours (Mussah et al., 2024). The overall aim of this study is to assess the LOS during on- and off-peak conditions using traffic simulation and autonomous vehicle detection, focusing on key intersections such as Moylapota, Gollamari, Sonadanga, and Shibbari, with particular emphasis on the Moylapota intersection.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

Five critical intersections of Khulna—Moylapota, Gollamari, Sonadanga and Shibbari were selected for this research. Then the research was conducted on Moylapota intersection.

2.2. Method

The method consists of two main phases - Phase I: Computer Vision-based Detection and Data Extraction, and Phase II: Simulation and LOS Evaluation.

Phase I: Traffic videos were recorded at intersection during both peak and off-peak hours to capture variations in flow, composition, and movement behavior. The recorded videos were then converted into frames with 25 frame intervals and some frames were removed. Then the images were uploaded in Roboflow

platform and annotated for 11 distinct vehicle classes bicycle, bike, bus, car, cng, easybike, leguna, rickshaw, truck, van, wheelbarrow. Then vehicle datasets of BD vehicles downloaded from Roboflow Universe which had 15 classes. So the extra 4 classes (boat, horsecart, tractor, launch) were removed and then reindexed the dataset using python script. Then this modified dataset was uploaded in Roboflow and combined with the previous annotated frames and then combined dataset was exported in yolov5, yolov8, yolov9 and yolo11 formats in train (70%), val (20%) and test (10%) groups with 640 x 640 resizing condition. A dataset of total 10,653 labeled images were used to train yolov5nu, yolov8n, yolov9t, yolo11n models which are ultrafast and lightweight object detection models introduced by Ultralytics, in kaggle notebook using PyTorch with optimized hyperparameters for learning rate, batch size, and image resolution (640×640). The YOLO architecture treats object detection as a regression problem: dividing each image into grids, predicting bounding boxes, and assigning class probabilities directly. The prediction accuracy of these models was evaluated using Precision, Recall, and Mean Average Precision (mAP) metrics at IoU thresholds of 0.50 and 0.50–0.95. The evaluation results, summarized in Table 1, indicate that yolo11n outperformed earlier YOLO versions across all key object detection metrics on the traffic detection dataset.

Table 1. Performance Metrics

Class	yolov5nu	yolov8n	yolov9t	yolo11n
Precision	0.885	0.893	0.878	0.896
Recall	0.766	0.779	0.793	0.795
mAP50	0.863	0.869	0.876	0.882
mAP50-90	0.613	0.629	0.652	0.653

These metrics indicate that the model reliability. distinguished between vehicle types, even under occlusion, shadow, or poor lighting conditions that challenges typical in Bangladeshi urban environments. The accuracy of the model was further validated using

IoU (Intersection-over-Union) analysis, which measured the degree of overlap between predicted and actual bounding boxes showed in Figure 1.

Fig 1. Intersection-over-Union (IoU)

Once the vehicle detection process was completed, the extracted counts were converted into Passenger Car Unit (PCU) equivalents to ensure comparability between heterogeneous traffic classes. Then two Py desktop apps were developed using Computer Vision and GUI (Graphical User Interface) integrated python scripts with yolo11n model to extract the vehicle classes counting and traffic volume (PCU/hr) data respectively and export the data in xlsx, csv and json formats. Then model and tally counting were compared for error calculation.

Phase II: The model of the intersection was drawn with geometrical details, routes and inputted the volume data (PCU/hr).

Fig 2. Intersection model and Routes

Then the vehicle composition data was inserted for each road in both on and off-peak time. Then the base line simulations were conducted for both on and off-peak time.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Error Calculation

The error calculation was done using model and tally counting data. The error data is shown in the figure 3.

Fig 3. Error Calculations

3.2. LOS and Vehicle Delay

The Los is A in both on peak and off peak as vehicle delays in both on peak and off peak are less than 10 seconds. and delays averaging **4.2 sec/veh** and **3.9 sec/veh**, respectively. On-peak delays were consistently higher.

4. Conclusion

The integrated YOLO11n-based vehicle detection and VISSIM simulation framework indicates that the Moylapota intersection operates at LOS A during both peak and off-peak periods, with average vehicle delays of less than 10 seconds, reflecting efficient signal performance under mixed traffic conditions. However, the results may be slightly affected by the use of low-resolution video during image annotation, the 600-second simulation limitation of the VISSIM student version despite having 1-hour field data, and minor detection and tracking inaccuracies due to occlusion, fast-moving vehicles, camera angle, lighting variations, and other environmental factors.

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Machine Learning based Soil Salinity Vulnerability Assessment using Geo-spatial Techniques in Southwestern Bangladesh

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Keywords

Bangladesh, machine learning, remote sensing, soil salinity.

1. Introduction

Soil degradation through salinization poses a critical challenge to agricultural productivity, food security, and ecological balance, especially in arid and coastal regions. The southwestern coastal belt of Bangladesh is highly susceptible to salinity intrusion due to tidal flooding, unsustainable irrigation, and sea-level rise. Traditional soil analysis techniques are labor-intensive and spatially limited, highlighting the need for remote sensing and machine learning approaches for accurate and scalable soil salinity mapping. This study aims to detect, model, and map soil salinity using multispectral satellite imagery and machine learning algorithms to enhance land management and adaptation strategies in climate-vulnerable coastal zones.

2. Materials and Methods

The study area covers the Khulna Division of southwestern Bangladesh, encompassing approximately 22,000 km² of low-lying coastal terrain prone to salinity intrusion. Multispectral data were obtained from Landsat 8 OLI and Sentinel-2A MSI satellites, alongside topographic indices derived from the CGIAR SRTM90 Digital Elevation Model. Ground-truth electrical conductivity (EC) samples were collected and georeferenced. Feature engineering included the derivation of vegetation, moisture, and salinity indices such as NDVI, NDWI, NDSI, MSI, and EVI, along with topographical attributes like slope, elevation, and distance to rivers. Data preprocessing involved atmospheric correction, spatial harmonization, and outlier detection using Isolation Forest. Logarithmic transformation was applied to normalize EC distributions. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to manage multicollinearity among predictors. Six supervised regression algorithms AdaBoost, XGBoost, LightGBM, Random Forest, ElasticNet, and a Stacking Ensemble were trained and validated using an 80/20 train-test split. Model tuning was optimized with Optuna, and

performance was evaluated through R², Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). Spatial prediction maps were generated for the best-performing models.

3. Results and Discussion

Model performance varied significantly across preprocessing scenarios with log transformations. The boosting algorithms XGBoost and AdaBoost outperformed others, achieving R² values of 0.838 and 0.857 with RMSE below 0.9. These models effectively captured nonlinear relationships between spectral indices and soil salinity. Random Forest exhibited moderate accuracy (R² = 0.74), while ElasticNet and the Stacking Ensemble showed weaker performance due to linearity assumptions and limited training data among three scenarios (Table 1).

Feature importance analysis revealed that NDWI, NDSI₁, NDSI₂, MSI, and EVI were the most influential predictors, reflecting vegetation moisture and salt stress. Elevation and distance to river showed inverse relationships with salinity, indicating higher salt accumulation in low-lying tidal zones. Spatial predictions identified high salinity zones across Satkhira and southwestern Khulna, with salinity decreasing eastward toward Jashore and Kushtia. These spatial trends align with observed hydro-salinization patterns and previous regional studies; as per shown in Figure 1. Figure 1 (b) and (d) shows outputs with outliers replaced by median.

Table 1. Model Comparison in outliers replaced by median scenario

Model	R ²	MAE	RMSE
AdaBoost	0.857	0.540	0.844
XGBoost	0.833	0.393	0.914
LightGBM	0.440	0.763	1.674
Stacking Ensemble	0.379	0.975	1.762
Random Forest	0.346	0.891	1.808
ElasticNet	-0.060	1.196	2.302

Geospatial analyses using Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA) and Getis-Ord G_i^* confirmed statistically significant clusters of high salinity along coastal embankments and aquaculture areas. These results highlight the utility of machine learning for capturing the spatial complexity of salinization processes. The study also emphasizes that appropriate preprocessing, especially log transformation and outlier control, is vital for robust model performance.

Fig 1. Maps using ML Models (a) with outliers excluded; (b) with outliers replaced with median; (c) LISA and Getis ord G_i^* output of AdaBoost; (d) LISA and Getis ord G_i^* output of RF

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Conclusion

This study successfully integrated remote sensing and machine learning techniques to map soil salinity in the coastal region of southwestern Bangladesh. Boosting algorithms demonstrated superior predictive accuracy and stability, highlighting their suitability for environmental modeling. The workflow established a scalable and reproducible framework for soil salinity prediction, capable of supporting climate-resilient agricultural planning. Future research should incorporate multi-temporal satellite data and deep learning models to capture seasonal and nonlinear salinity dynamics, as well as socio-economic layers for comprehensive vulnerability mapping

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Assessment of Urban Thermal Comfort Level Changes with Urban Expansion Intensity in Khulna City and Adjacent Areas

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Keywords

Urban Heat Island (UHI), Land Surface Temperature (LST), Urban Thermal Field Variance Index (UTFVI), Urban Expansion Intensity Index (UEII)

1. Introduction

The landscape of Khulna has been altered by the rapid and sometimes unplanned nature of urban expansion. This has led to a higher Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect and lower ecological comfort (Ashraf M. Dewan, 2009). The increased use of impervious materials such as concrete and asphalt, replacing vegetated areas, has increased Land Surface Temperature (LST) and thermal stress. While a considerable amount of research has focused on the urban thermal environment of Dhaka and other large cities in Bangladesh, very little research has been conducted to assess the ecological comfort of Khulna City using quantitative measures such as the Urban Thermal Field Variance Index (UTFVI) and the Urban Expansion Intensity Index (UEII). The study aims to evaluate the effect of urban expansion from 2015 to 2025 on land surface temperature, ecological stability, and thermal comfort in and around Khulna City using the UTFVI and UEII. This study addresses the gap in understanding how urban expansion intensity (UEII) correlates with thermal comfort changes (UTFVI) in Khulna, a secondary city where rapid peri-urban growth impacts ecological stability.

2. Materials and Methods

The study used a remote sensing and GIS-based method with Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS satellite images from 2015, 2020, and 2025. These images came from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer platform. Each image had less than 10% cloud cover and was taken during the hot, dry season from April to October. This ensured consistency in analyzing surface temperatures. We gathered additional data from various sources, including administrative boundary shapefiles from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS) and surface emissivity data from the ASTER Global Emissivity Database (GEDv3), to improve the

accuracy of land surface temperature estimates (Ashraf M. Dewan, 2009).

We carried out preprocessing, atmospheric correction, and cloud masking in Google Earth Engine (GEE) using the LaSRC algorithm to reduce atmospheric distortion. We derived key spectral indices: NDVI for vegetation, NDBI for built-up intensity, and LST for surface heat distribution. UTFVI assessed ecological comfort across six stress levels. UEII measured urban growth intensity across thanas (Imran et al., 2021). We used zonal statistics and Pearson correlation to explore relationships among these indices. This was supported by a Random Forest (RF) based LULC classification for precise temporal comparisons of urban expansion (Abubakar Abubakar et al., n.d.; Morshed et al., 2022).

3. Results and Discussion

I. Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) Change

Between 2015 and 2025, Khulna's built-up area grew by 63.7%, increasing from 61.91 km² to 101.33 km². This expansion mainly occurred in Rupsha, Daulatpur, and Khalishpur. During the same period, vegetation decreased by 12.9%. Water bodies shrank by 58%, showing rapid urban spread and fewer ecological buffers.

Fig 1. LULC Changes Map

II. Land Surface Temperature (LST)

Average surface temperatures increased by 7 to 9°C, exceeding 50°C in urban centers by 2025. Vegetated areas stayed cooler, showing a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.72$) with land surface temperature. In

contrast, built-up areas showed a positive correlation ($r = 0.87$). This confirms that urban growth drives surface heating.

III. Urban Heat Island (UHI) Phenomenon

From 2015 to 2025, Sonadanga, Khalishpur, and Rupsha became major heat zones. Temperature differences reached up to $+9.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ between urban and rural areas. Rapid land use changes and the loss of vegetation increased the UHI footprint. Meanwhile, green spaces and water areas helped cool the environment.

IV. Urban Thermal Field Variance Index (UTFVI)

Fig 2. UTFVI Classes Map

Urban UTFVI analysis showed that comfortable zones decreased from 264.94 km^2 in 2015 to 241.97 km^2 in 2025. At the same time, “worse” and “worst” comfort zones increased from 114.88 km^2 to 163.8 km^2 . The hottest areas were Khalishpur, Sonadanga, and Rupsha. There, dense development increased surface heating. Terokhada was an exception. It maintained better thermal comfort because of its vegetation cover, low-density housing, and preserved wetlands. These features helped regulate heat and support ecological balance.

V. Expansion Intensity (UEII)

UEII values indicated faster urban growth in Batiaghata (3.75), Terokhada (2.57), and Daulatpur (1.67) during 2020 to 2025, while areas like Sonadanga experienced stagnation. Regions with higher UEII scores corresponded with higher UTFVI values, showing that rapid urban growth leads to more thermal stress.

Table 1: Key Results Summary (2015–2025)

Indicator	Change
Built-up Area	↑ 63.7% increase
Vegetation Cover	↓ 12.9% decrease
Mean LST	↑ 7–9°C rise
Comfortable Zones (UTFVI)	↓ 8.7% reduction
Heat-Stressed Zones (UTFVI)	↑ 42.6% expansion
LST-NDVI Correlation	$r = -0.72$ (negative)
LST-NDBI Correlation	$r = 0.87$ (positive)

From Table 1, overall, the results show that rapid urban growth in Khulna has noticeably raised surface temperatures and decreased ecological comfort. The

loss of vegetation and the spread of buildings have increased thermal stress, changing once-comfortable areas into new urban heat zones throughout the city and its surroundings.

4. Conclusion

The study shows a clear connection between urban growth and the decline of thermal comfort in Khulna. From 2015 to 2025, higher building density and loss of vegetation raised land surface temperature (LST) and urban thermal comfort index (UTFVI) values. This increase in heat stress spread from the city center to the surrounding areas. These findings highlight that unchecked urban expansion harms the environment and reduces the quality of life. To reduce the urban heat island (UHI) effect, sustainable actions are essential. Urban greening, reflective building materials, green roofs, and wetland protection can all help. Adding UTFVI-UEII monitoring systems to urban policy will support data-driven and climate-resilient planning for Khulna and other rapidly growing cities in Bangladesh.

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Mapping Groundwater Potential Zones using Fuzzy AHP and Random Forest: A Comparative Analysis

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Keywords

Fuzzy AHP, GIS, groundwater potential zone, Random Forest

1. Introduction

Groundwater serves as an essential resource for various applications, including domestic, agricultural, and industrial needs, especially in the Khulna Division of Bangladesh, where surface water frequently suffers from salinity or contamination (Shivakoti, 2016). The growing population, intensified agricultural practices and climate-related challenges like drought and rising sea levels have intensified the strain on groundwater resources, leading to significant concerns regarding their long-term viability (Chen et al., 2025). This investigation seeks to delineate and assess Groundwater Potential Zones (GWPZs) throughout the Khulna Division by employing the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FuzzyAHP) alongside the Random Forest (RF) machine learning model. Spatial datasets that include topographic, geological, land use, soil and climatic factors are examined to assess the primary influences on groundwater occurrence. The evaluation of model performance is conducted through the use of Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves and Area Under the Curve (AUC) metrics, which are essential for confirming accuracy and reliability (Raisa et al., 2024). The findings of this study aim to enhance sustainable groundwater management through the provision of data-driven insights that support evidence-based policymaking, irrigation planning and aquifer conservation.

2. Materials and Methods

A thorough study was conducted on 219 well locations to assess GWPZs across various geological and topographical contexts in Khulna Division. Total 16 factors were selected by conducting vast literature review. Sixteen thematic layers were created across four distinct categories: topographical, land-use and geological, meteorological and socio-economic. Topographical factors were obtained from the 30 m SRTM DEM, land-use and geology data were sourced from Sentinel-2 imagery via Google Earth Engine, as well as from

the GSB and the BARC. Meteorological variables were obtained from the Bangladesh Meteorological Department (BMD). Additionally, socio-economic factors were gathered from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (2022). All datasets underwent normalization on a 0–1 scale and were subsequently integrated through FuzzyAHP process (Sarkar et al., 2022). The Random Forest (RF) algorithm confirmed the findings through ROC and AUC metrics to evaluate model precision.

3. Results and Discussion

Topographical Factors- After raster conversion, scaling and reclassification, six topographical factors—elevation, slope, curvature, roughness, drainage density and Topographic Wetness Index (TWI)—were analyzed to understand their influence on GWPZs in Khulna Division. The elevation ranges from –43 m in Satkhira and parts of Khulna to 99 m in Meherpur and Kushtia, where lower areas favor water accumulation and higher zones promote runoff. Most of the division, exhibits gentle slopes near 0°, enhancing infiltration potential. Moderate curvature dominates across the region.

Fig 1: Topographical factors

The area is generally flat with low roughness values. Drainage density ranges from 0 to 1.14 km/km², highest in Khulna and Magura, suggesting lower infiltration potential there. TWI values (3.29–25.70) are moderate across most districts, implying balanced soil moisture and limited topographic control on recharge. **Land-use and Geological Factors-**The Land Use Land Cover (LULC) includes forest, barren land, built-up areas, vegetation, and water bodies. The southern region (Khulna and Satkhira) is dominated by Sundarbans

forest, while the north features agriculture and urban land. Geologically, the south consists of mangrove swamp, marsh clay, and tidal deposits, whereas the north and center have deltaic silt and sand, allowing better groundwater recharge. Soil ranges from calcareous floodplain in the north to peat and acid sulphate in the south, with texture shifting from clay in coastal areas to loam inland. As a result, soil permeability is low in coastal zones but moderate to high in northern regions, favoring groundwater infiltration.

Fig 2: Land-use, geological, and meteorological factors

Meteorological Factors-These factors show a clear north-south gradient. Annual rainfall ranges from 5.17 mm to 7.29 mm, with higher values in southern areas like Khulna, Bagerhat, and the Sundarbans due to the Bay of Bengal's influence. Similarly, relative humidity (71.75%–76.04%) increases toward the coast, while northern regions such as Jessore remain drier.

Socio-Economic Factors-These factors exhibit significant spatial variability that directly influences groundwater dependency and accessibility.

Fig 3: Socio-economic factors

Population density ranges from 441.88 to 1330.96 persons/km², highest in northern urban areas and lowest in the southern coastal belt near the Sundarbans. Access to tap water is limited (1.58%–7.73%), with slightly better availability in the north. In contrast, tubewell access is widespread (53%–98%), especially in central and western regions.

Ground Water Potential Zone-

Fig 4: Relative importance of factors
According to both models, 'access to tubewell' is the most relevant factor.

Fig 5: Groundwater potential zone (a) RF (b) fuzzyAHP

Both maps show almost similar layout. But Random Forest method shows high accuracy with 86.39% where FuzzyAHP shows 78.54%.

Fig 6: ROC curve for RF and fuzzyAHP

4. Conclusion

This study integrated FuzzyAHP and Random Forest (RF) models to delineate GWPZs across the Khulna Division. Results indicate that Satkhira and Bagerhat possess very high groundwater potential, while Kushtia and Chuadanga show very low potential. The RF model achieved 86.39% accuracy, demonstrating superior performance over FuzzyAHP. Among all parameters, 'access to tubewell' was identified as the most influential factor, followed by population density, access to tap water, soil type and rainfall. Most of the region falls within the moderate potential zone, covering 32% and 29% of the area in RF and FuzzyAHP models, respectively. These findings highlight the importance of integrating socio-economic and environmental variables for accurate groundwater assessment and sustainable water resource management in southwestern Bangladesh

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Hybrid Wind-Solar Energy Potential Assessment in the Coastal Regions of Bangladesh

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Keywords

Climate adaptation, Decarbonization, Renewable energy, Temporal dynamics of wind-solar indices.

1. Introduction

The continued dominance of fossil fuels in the energy sector of Bangladesh increases greenhouse gas emissions and climatic vulnerability (Hossain, 2024). Hybrid wind solar systems provide a sustainable alternative, especially in coastal areas where monsoon winds and intense solar radiation coincide (Babatunde et al., 2020). Prior studies overlooked national planning restrictions and temporal dynamics in favor of static datasets (Aghaloo et al., 2023; Koc et al., 2019). This study integrates GIS-BWM-Fuzzy spatial analysis with decade-long ERA5 and PVOUT data for higher accuracy. This study offers a reproducible framework for guiding renewable energy policy and land-use planning to support SDG 7 and Bangladesh's target of 40% renewable energy capacity by 2041.

2. Materials and Methods

This study focused on 13 coastal districts of Bangladesh that are located along the Bay of Bengal (Fig 1) and have significant wind regimes and solar radiation. A comprehensive GIS-based Multi Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) framework was developed, which included the Best-Worst Method (BWM) for assigning optimal weights to 14 technical, environmental and socioeconomic factors (60%, 21%, and 19%). The final hybrid suitability surface was generated using fuzzy membership functions and the Fuzzy Gamma ($\gamma = 0.9$) overlay operator, while ecologically sensitive areas were excluded using a Boolean constraint model. In ArcGIS 10.8, all this geospatial processing was carried out. For temporal analysis, ten years ERA5 reanalysis data (2014–2023) were used to calculate mean wind speed, energy, direction and frequency using derived u-v components and Betz-based power equations in the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform. The Global Solar Atlas was used to obtain so-

lar PVOUT, which represents the estimated photovoltaic power output (kWh/kWp/day) from a standard solar photovoltaic system, modeled from satellite-based solar irradiation data. To cross-validate GIS-derived suitability zones with high-frequency hybrid areas identified in the GEE platform, a spatial agreement analysis was conducted.

Fig 1. Map of study area.

3. Results and Discussion

The final hybrid suitability surface (Fig 2) was generated using the GIS-BWM-Fuzzy MCDM framework which determined that 4.66% (1,121 km²) of the coastal area of Bangladesh is highly suitable for hybrid wind-solar development, compared to Aghaloo et al. (2023), who indicated 11% suitable areas in Bangladesh and this study presents a more targeted coastal evaluation enhanced through stricter exclusion and multi-year temporal validation. These high-potential areas were centered in Cox's Bazar, Chittagong and Bhola. The weighting hierarchy was dominated by technical characteristics, highlighting the significance of wind speed and solar irradiation in identifying suitable zones. By eliminating 28.3% of unsuitable land, Boolean exclusion modeling improved site selection and guaranteed environmentally compliant energy zoning.

The spatial coherence of hybrid resources was emphasized by temporal analysis in the GEE Platform (Fig 3), where the eastern coastal belt showed the highest concentration of regions surpassing the combined wind frequency (wind speeds ≥ 4 m/s on over 40 % of days) and PVOOUT (≥ 4 kWh/kWp/day) thresholds.

Fig 2. Final hybrid suitability map of coastal Bangladesh.

Fig 3. Hybrid frequency suitability map for coastal Bangladesh.

Cross-validation of GIS-derived and GEE-identified zones (Fig 4) found 67.6% geographical agreement showing the model's temporal robustness and reliability.

The spatial-temporal framework shows that incorporating long-term temporal performance reduces and improves priority areas for pilot deployment which is largely neglected in prior GIS-only studies (Koc et al., 2019).

Fig 4. Spatial agreement between GIS and GEE suitability.

4. Conclusion

This study developed an integrated spatial-temporal framework that incorporated a GIS-MCDM-BWM-Fuzzy-GEE framework, utilizing multiple wind-solar indices. The model provides spatial precision and temporal reliability, identifying the eastern coastal belt particularly Cox's Bazar, Chittagong and Bhola as the most promising hybrid energy corridor. Despite relying on secondary datasets and missing ground-based validation, the framework serves as a transferable, climate-informed tool for guiding decentralized hybrid energy development. Future work may include off-shore wind integration. This study directly contributes to SDG 7.

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Determinants of Household Adaptive Capacity Among Migrant and Non-Migrant Households: Evidence from Coastal Bangladesh

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Keywords

Adaptive capacity, adaptive capacity index, beta regression, migrant and non-migrant households.

1. Introduction

Climate change has the most visible impacts in low- and middle-income countries, where it significantly affects the livelihood security of poor and marginalized people. However, the adaptive capacity of coastal households plays a crucial role in minimizing the consequences of climate change, as it enables systems to adjust effectively to environmental changes. Households' adaptive capacity to climate change varies considerably between migrant and non-migrant households [2]. Several authors have different understandings regarding migrant and non-migrant households' adaptive capacity. Szaboova et al. [4] argued that migrant households may enhance adaptive capacity through remittances, improving material well-being, while non-migrant households often face increased vulnerability. On the contrary, Abel et al. [1] highlighted that migrant households encounter diverse forms of insecurity and precarity in sustaining expenditures from remittances, which could become unsustainable and even maladaptive in the long run, thereby limiting the adaptive capacity of migrant households. Therefore, this research aims to identify the adaptive capacity differentials between migrant and non-migrant households and the major determinants of household adaptive capacity.

2. Materials and Methods

Initially, Dacope Upazila in Khulna District is segmented into five zones according to their proximity to the coast, with Sutharkhali and Tildanga unions designated as the target areas. Subsequently, we randomly selected ten Mohallas (neighbourhood-level administrative units) to ensure sufficient spatial coverage of the study area, utilising ArcMap 10.8, which resulted in a total of 416 households. By utilising Yamane's [5] formula, we selected a sample of 100 households- comprising 50 migrants and 50 non-migrants- from the 10 targeted Mohallas through simple random sampling, representing 24% of the total population. Here,

migrant households are defined as those with at least one family member who has previously migrated, either domestically or internationally, in pursuit of improved livelihoods and to support their families, whereas non-migrant households consist of all family members who are already residing in that location. A total of 29 variables related to adaptive capacity and 18 household essential factors (including basic socio-economic, demographic, and institutional factors) have been selected based on a comprehensive literature review. Furthermore, variables related to adaptive capacity are examined according to the well-established framework of five assets- physical, financial, social, natural, and human assets [3]. In the analytical section, the Adaptive Capacity Index (ACI) is initially employed to evaluate the difference in adaptive capacity between migrant and non-migrant households. The ACI equations were developed based on the widely acknowledged Human Development Index (HDI), as detailed in HDI [6]. Next, the Beta Regression (BR) model is conducted to determine which household factors most significantly influence the development of household adaptive capacity within coastal communities. The dependent variable is the ACI value (for both migrant and non-migrant households), while the independent variables consist of essential household factors. The ACI range extends from 0 to 1, which is ideal for the BR model. The predictive capability of this model is substantial ($\text{Chi}^2 = 94.79$, $P \text{ value} = 0.0000 < 0.05$, $\text{Log likelihood} = 75.298$). The log likelihood and p-value indicate that the model is accurate and statistically significant.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Adaptive Capacity Differential Among Migrant and Non-migrant Households

ACI is used to investigate the difference in adaptive capacity between migrant and non-migrant households. The results indicate that the overall adaptive capacity index values of non-migrant households are higher compared to migrant households, although the difference is minimal. Migrant households show higher index values for the physical and financial asset dimen-

sions than non-migrant households, whereas non-migrant households display higher index values in the social, natural, and human asset dimensions than migrant households.

Fig 1. Dimensional contribution of ACI values

3.2. Factors Influencing Household Adaptive Capacity

It is well recognized that adaptive capacity depends on household factors such as ownership of land, quantity of household assets, financial remittances, education level, number of migrant members, total savings, and income. The results of the BR model challenge the traditional understanding that financial remittances are a major factor in increasing households' capacity to adapt to adverse situations, revealing that the financial remittance variable does not significantly influence households' adaptive capacity. However, factors such as land ownership, higher secondary and university education, full understanding of early warning systems, access to disaster preparedness training, knowledge about climate change, joint decision-making (by both male and female) on household expenditure, number of organizational memberships, and number of employed female members contribute to increasing household adaptive capacity. The findings also reveal that land ownership slightly enhances adaptive capacity, whereas the number of organizational memberships (OR = 1.261) and employed female members (OR = 1.286) significantly improve household adaptive capacity. Among categorical factors, families with higher secondary (OR = 1.835) and university or college education (OR = 2.529) have greater adaptive capacity than those without education. Individuals with a thorough understanding of early warning systems (OR = 1.495) and knowledge of climate change (OR = 1.367) demonstrate greater adaptive potential. Furthermore, families who make joint expenditure decisions (OR = 1.043) are more adaptable than those in which only males decide. These findings indicate that education, awareness, women's participation, and community involvement play more important roles in developing adaptive capacity than financial remittances alone.

Conclusion

The major findings of this study show that migrant households possess greater physical and financial assets than non-migrant households but have lower social, natural, and human assets. In the absence of male

members, migrant households in their places of origin become socially isolated and detached, with limited access to natural assets. Hence, this study will assist policymakers in determining priority-based dimensional upliftment strategies for both migrants and non-migrants. The findings also show that various household factors- such as land ownership, access to preparedness training, organizational memberships, and the employment of female members significantly impact the growth of household adaptive capacity, whereas financial remittance does not. Thus, this study will inform rural planners and policymakers about which components should be prioritized in policy measures to enhance rural households' adaptive capacity.

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Assessment of Urban Housing Vulnerabilities: A Modified Severity Index Approach to Slum Conditions in Khulna’s Rupsha Char, Khora, and Kuli Bagan Slum

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Keywords

Analytical Hierarchy Process, Slum Severity Index, Urban Housing Vulnerability, Sustainable Development Goal 11, Khulna City

1. Introduction

Rapid urbanization in Khulna has driven the expansion of informal settlements, resulting in overcrowding, inadequate housing, and insufficient access to essential services. This study assesses housing-related vulnerabilities in three major slum areas Rupsha Char, Khora, and Kuli Bagan using a modified Slum Severity Index (SSI). The research aims to identify the intensity and nature of multiple housing deprivations and propose data-driven insights for sustainable urban planning aligned with SDG 11. The growing pace of urbanization in developing cities has intensified housing inequalities and increased vulnerability among low-income populations (UN-Habitat, 2020). Previous studies have emphasized that identifying slum severity through multidimensional frameworks is crucial for sustainable planning (Patel et al., 2020; Balachandran & Thennakoon, 2023).

2. Materials and Methods

The study focuses on three informal settlements in Khulna Rupsha Char, Khora, and Kuli Bagan selected for their dense population, poor housing, and high environmental risk.

Fig 1: Study Slums

A mixed-method approach was adopted, combining quantitative household surveys and qualitative observations. The SSI framework was modified using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to assign realistic weights to key vulnerability dimensions: basic urban services, housing quality, environmental risk, socioeconomic inclusion, and accessibility (Ishizaka & Labib, 2009; Saaty, 2008).

Primary data were collected from 117 households across the three slums, supported by field observations and resident interviews, focusing on indicators like housing structure, access to water, sanitation, electricity, drainage, healthcare, education, and income stability (UN-Habitat, 2016; Patel, Shah, & Beauregard, 2020). Based on the UN-Habitat framework, all variables were categorized under five major dimensions: (i) Access to Basic Urban Services, (ii) Housing Quality and Security, (iii) Environmental Risk and Resilience, (iv) Socioeconomic Status and Inclusion, and (v) Accessibility to Public Facilities (Balachandran & Thennakoon, 2023; Hick, Pomati, & Stephens, 2022).

The AHP method was then used to compare these factors pairwise and calculate their relative importance (Saaty, 2008; Ishizaka & Labib, 2009). The Consistency Ratio (CR) values were confirmed to be within the acceptable range (<10%), ensuring reliable weighting. Each factor’s Factor Assessment Score (FAS) was multiplied by its Realistic Weight (RW) to compute the final Slum Severity Index (SSI) (Patel et al., 2020; Ayala & Ruiz, 2008). These scores were multiplied by their respective AHP weights to compute the final Slum Severity Index (SSI) using the formula:

$$SSI = \sum (RW_i \times FAS_i) \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

The resulting SSI scores were graded from A (Good) to E (Extreme) to indicate levels of deprivation. Statistical analyses, including correlation, regression, and chi-square tests, were then conducted to identify key factors influencing vulnerability (Popogbe, 2021; Balachandran & Thennakoon, 2023).

3. Results and Discussion

Findings revealed significant variation in vulnerability across slums. The overall SSI scores were Khora (102.3, Grade D), Rupsha Char (143.33, Grade D), and Kuli Bagan (228.01, Grade C), indicating critical to poor living conditions. Consistent with studies in South Asian informal settlements, the most significant sub-factors were flood resilience, durable housing, and access to safe drinking water (Patel, Shah, & Beauregard, 2020; Balachandran & Thennakoon, 2023).

Correlation analyses confirmed that socioeconomic stability and infrastructure deficits strongly affect overall vulnerability, reinforcing the multidimensional nature of housing deprivation as highlighted by (Hick, Pomati, & Stephens, 2022). The AHP-weighted SSI approach produced more context-specific results than traditional equal-weight models.

Fig 2: Sources of Drinking Water in the Study Slums

Most households in Rupsha Char and Kuli Bagan use tube wells, Khora Slum relies on public taps, and a few have piped water, indicating limited access to safe drinking water.

Fig 3: Types of Sanitation Facilities Available by Slum Dwellers

Most use shared improved toilets, but unimproved/open ones are common, and private improved toilets are rare, showing poor sanitation.

Table 1: Correlation of Five Major Factors with Slum Severity Index (SSI) across the three slums

Major Factors	Spearman's Correlation Coefficient		
	Khora Slum	Kuli Bagan Slum	Rupsha Char Slum
Access to Basic Urban Services	0.210	0.298	0.266
Housing Quality and Security	0.330	0.185	0.295
Accessibility to Public Facilities	0.626	0.634	0.648

Environmental Risk and Resilience	0.429	0.225	0.394
Socioeconomic Status and Social Inclusion	0.759	0.383	0.202

Correlation analysis showed that all five factors strongly relate to overall slum severity. Where Khora Slum was found to be the most vulnerable overall. Kuli Bagan was less vulnerable, but still faced major challenges.

4. Conclusion

The study finds that Khulna's Rupsha Char, Khora, and Kuli Bagan slums face poor living conditions, limited basic services, and environmental risks, highlighting the urgent need for targeted urban interventions. By integrating AHP with SSI, the research provides a reliable tool for prioritizing slum improvement actions. Planners and policymakers can use these insights to allocate resources effectively, improve housing resilience, and promote inclusive and sustainable urban development.

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Urban Growth Dynamics and Socio-economic Drivers in Khulna: A Spatiotemporal Perspective

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Keywords

Impervious surface area (ISA), Remote sensing and GIS, Socioeconomic drivers, Urbanization.

1. Introduction

Urbanization is transforming global land use and ecosystems, with impervious surfaces serving as an effective proxy for monitoring these changes through remote sensing [1]. Previous studies on Khulna focused mainly on physical land-cover change and lacked validated post-2020 integration of socio-economic drivers. This study quantifies the spatiotemporal expansion of impervious surfaces in Khulna City Corporation (KCC) from 2000 to 2024 using the CART classification algorithm on multi-temporal Landsat imagery. Spatial-statistical tools—mean center shift, standard deviational ellipse, and zonal statistics—analyzed growth magnitude and direction, while accuracy metrics validated results. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) associated physical expansion with socio-economic factors. By integrating remote sensing and socio-economic analysis, this study provides validated post-2020 evidence of Khulna’s urban growth.

2. Materials and Methods

The study area, Khulna City Corporation (50.61 km²), lies at the confluence of the Rupsha and Bhairab rivers in southwestern Bangladesh (Figure 1).

Fig 1. Map of study area - Khulna City Corporation (KCC)

Multi-temporal Landsat 5 TM (2000), 7 ETM+ (2010), and 8 OLI/TIRS (2020 and 2024) images were sourced from USGS and processed in Google Earth Engine. Cloud-free composites were generated using `simpleComposite()` to reduce atmospheric noise and ensure radiometric consistency. All imagery was clipped to KCC boundaries.

Impervious and non-impervious classes were produced via the CART algorithm. Overall accuracies ranged 65–85 %, with a maximum Kappa value of 0.69 (2020) — indicating substantial agreement [2], [3].

Fig 2. Methodological framework of the study

Spatial-statistical analyses in ArcGIS Pro measured urban morphology through Weighted Mean Center (WMC), Linear Directional Mean (LDM), and Standard Deviational Ellipse (SDE). Socio-economic variables were obtained from BBS census reports [5] and PCA was used to assess socio-economic drivers of urban growth—population, literacy, employment, poverty, and slum prevalence (Figure 2 [1]).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Main text

Urban expansion in KCC showed a distinct directional pattern between 2000 and 2024. Total impervious surface increased

from 16.57 km² (2000) to 26.33 km² (2024), reflecting continuous expansion, with the sharpest rise from 2010–2020 (Table 1). Growth aligned mainly with industrial corridors and peri-urban roads. Spatial analysis revealed a clear northeast-southwest trajectory, with built-up areas densifying around Sonadanga and Kotwali thanas. Mean-center migration indicated a 1.6 km northeastward shift of the urban core, while Standard Deviational Ellipse (SDE) results showed progressive spreading but lower flatness ratios, implying a more even distribution of built-up land.

Fig 3. Mean center displacement and standard deviational ellipses of KCC (2000-2024)

The expansion ratio and intensity index confirm that 2000-2010 was the most dynamic phase ($\approx 31\%$ growth), followed by a slower but more integrated spread after 2020 (Table 1). These findings align with earlier studies identifying population growth and industrial development as key drivers in Khulna [1]. Unlike previous research, this study incorporates post-2020 satellite data and socio-economic variables through PCA.

Directional distribution of impervious-surface expansion showing northeastward migration of Khulna’s urban core. The ellipses represent dispersion patterns derived from weighted-mean center and standard-deviation ellipse analyses. The northeastward expansion and rising impervious coverage highlight the need for transport planning, flood resilience, and improved peri-urban services.

Table 1. Change in impervious area of KCC from 2000 to 2024

Research period	2000-2010	2010-2020	2020-2024
Expansion ratio (%)	31.1963	8.8582	10.3672
Intensity Index (%)	3.1196	0.8858	2.5918

Source: Author’s analysis using Landsat imagery (2000-2024).

Conclusion

This research provides a validated post-2020 assessment of ISA in KCC by integrating remote sensing, spatial-statistical, and socio-economic analyses, explicitly linking physical land-cover change with socio-economic drivers. Multi-temporal impervious-surface mapping confirmed a sustained northeastward expansion driven by infrastructure, migration, and employment growth. The integration of zonal statistics, accuracy assessment, and PCA establishes a framework linking land-cover change with human-environment interactions. Findings support transport-oriented planning, climate-resilient infrastructure, and equitable service provision in Bangladesh’s rapidly urbanizing secondary cities.

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Assessing the Role of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in National Climate Change Policies and Dhaka’s Urban Plans

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Keywords

Climate adaptation, Dhaka, nature-based solutions, urban planning.

1. Introduction

Rapid urbanization, high population density, and environmental degradation make Dhaka one of the world’s most climate-vulnerable megacities. Conventional grey infrastructure is increasingly insufficient to manage flooding, heat stress, and waterlogging. Nature-based Solutions (NbS) offer a synergistic approach to address these challenges while providing social and ecological co-benefits. This study aims to: (1) evaluate the integration of NbS within Bangladesh’s national climate policies and Dhaka’s urban plans; (2) identify the key barriers to their effective implementation; and (3) propose a strategic framework to mainstream NbS into urban climate resilience practice.

2. Materials and Methods

The research employed a qualitative methodology, triangulating data from three primary sources to ensure robustness, as illustrated in Figure 1. First, a systematic document analysis was conducted on national policies (e.g., Five-Year Plans, Bangladesh Delta Plan 2100, National Adaptation Plan) and Dhaka’s urban plans (Structure Plan, Detailed Area Plan) from 2022–2035. Second, a comparative review of international NbS case studies (e.g., China’s Sponge City, New York’s Bluebelt) was performed to identify transferable lessons. Third, semi-structured interviews were held with key informants, including urban planners, policy-makers, and environmental scientists. While NVIVO 15 software was used to manage and thematically code the qualitative data from documents and interviews, the synthesis for decision-making was conducted manually to interpret recurring themes, operational gaps, and practitioner perspectives.

Fig 1. Research methodology flowchart

3. Results and Discussion

The analysis reveals a significant gap between policy rhetoric and operational implementation. At the national level, documents like the 8th Five Year Plan and the National Adaptation Plan (NAP) show a clear conceptual shift, explicitly recognizing and positioning NbS and ecosystem-based adaptation as central strategies. However, this high-level intent is not translated into actionable mandates. The study identified three primary barriers to implementation:

Institutional Fragmentation: Ambiguous and overlapping responsibilities across agencies like RAJUK, city corporations, and national ministries prevent coordinated delivery.

Lack of Operational Guidelines: A critical absence of standardized NbS design standards, performance metrics, and monitoring protocols hinders consistent application and accountability.

Insufficient and Siloed Financing: Funding for NbS remains project-based, ad-hoc, and lacks dedicated, scalable financial instruments, keeping interventions at the pilot stage.

At the city level, while Dhaka’s Structure Plan and Detailed Area Plan reference green corridors and waterbody conservation, they lack the regulatory teeth for enforcement. Successful pilot projects like Hatirjheel demonstrate the viability of hybrid grey-green infrastructure, but they remain isolated examples. Comparative analysis indicates that overcoming these barriers requires strong national guidance, blended finance models, and clear performance monitoring—lessons that are relevant but must be adapted to Dhaka’s unique governance context.

Conclusion

Bangladesh has progressed in its conceptual appreciation of NbS, but a substantial implementation gap persists. To translate policy into practice, this study proposes a multi-pronged strategy. Key policy recommendations for Dhaka’s institutions include:

Develop NbS Operational Standards: The National Adaptation Plan should be supplemented with technical guidelines and mandatory monitoring metrics for urban projects.

Establish a Coordinating Body: Create an NbS platform with representatives from RAJUK, city corporations, and relevant ministries to align mandates and streamline approval.

Pilot Financially Sustainable Models: Launch demonstration projects in priority flood-prone wards, funded through blended finance mechanisms like public-private partnerships and targeted climate funds.

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Fig 2. Conceptual framework for Green Transferable Development Rights (G-TDRS)

Future research should focus on developing context-specific NbS performance indicators and exploring innovative financing instruments like Green TDRs to incentivize private sector investment. This strategic approach can bridge the current implementation gap and build a more resilient and livable Dhaka.

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Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) for Landslide Susceptibility Mapping at Kaptai Upazila

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Keywords

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), GIS, Kaptai Upazila, landslide susceptibility mapping, Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA).

1. Introduction

Landslides are a frequent and serious hazard that can cause a great deal of damage in Bangladesh's hilly areas. The Chittagong Hill Districts (CHD) experienced a succession of devastating landslide incidents that claimed the lives of more than 725 individuals from the year 2000 to 2018 (Sultana, 2020). Among the CHD, Rangamati district experienced the most severe adverse effects. A total of 126 lives were lost due to the landslides in the Rangamati district. The middle portion of the Rangamati District such as Kaokhali, Kaptai, and Rangamati Sadar, is characterized by a higher susceptibility to landslides compared to the northeastern and northern regions, including Baghaichari (Begum et al., 2020). Among the areas, Kaptai Upazila is in high risk for its elevated altitude, substantial precipitation and tourist attractions.

Therefore, this study's goal is to determine the locations in Kaptai Upazila that are most susceptible to landslides which has not been done yet for Bangladesh at the upazila-level scale. This has been achieved by developing a detailed susceptibility map using GIS and RS data through MCDA.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

Kaptai Upazila is located in the southern Rangamati district of Bangladesh. Covering 259 square km, it features a complex topography of low-lying alluvial plains and hilly terrain ranging from 5 to 425 meters above sea level making Kaptai highly vulnerable to frequent and destructive landslides.

Fig 1. Study area map

2.2. Methodology

In the literature, a number of methods and techniques have been developed over time to map the probability of landslides. GIS-MCDA is a robust method that use geographic information systems to analyze and predict the risks associated with landslides (Ahmed, 2021). This research utilized an integrated GIS-MCDA approach, selecting eight conditioning factors based on their established relevance in the study area: slope, elevation, aspect, distance to drainage, LULC, NDVI, rainfall, and distance to roads. Factors like lithology were excluded due to limited high-resolution geospatial data availability for the specific study area. Datasets were sourced from USGS and the Bangladesh Meteorological Department (BMD).

Primary weights were determined using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), incorporating opinions from 9 experts through a pair-wise comparison matrix. The final weights prioritizing slope and aspect yielded a Consistency Ratio (CR) of 0.09, validating the model's reliability (CR < 0.1).

Table 1. Final normalized weights for landslide factors

Criteria	Weighted Index	Consistency Vector
Slope	4.594	14.027
Aspect	2.857	14.466
Elevation	1.957	12.330
Distance to Drainage	0.769	9.769
LULC	0.821	9.256
NDVI	0.702	8.781
Rainfall	0.423	9.396
Distance to Road	0.237	9.995

Thematic layers were reclassified into five classes (1: Unsuitable to 5: High Suitability for landslide occurrence). Cutoff values were determined through literature and local history; for instance, NDVI values >0.36 differentiated dense vegetation from other land. The model's LULC accuracy was verified with a Kappa coefficient of 80%. A Weighted Overlay Analysis in

ArcMap 10.8.2 produced the final map, classified into three susceptibility zones: low, moderate, and high.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results

The spatial analysis revealed that 12.32% of Kaptai Upazila falls within the *low* susceptibility class, 81.15% within *moderate*, and 7.39% within *high* susceptibility zones. High-risk areas are primarily located along steep terrain and near major drainage and road corridors, particularly in Kaptai, Chitmaran, and Raikhali unions.

Fig 2. Landslide susceptibility mapping of kaptai upazila

Among the conditioning factors, slope played the dominant role, where areas exceeding 30° slope accounted for over 42% of total landslide occurrences. The area near Chandraghona union and Karnaphuli river has the area with slope more than 40°.

Elevation ranging between 100–400 m above sea level represented the most vulnerable class due to rapid runoff concentration.

Aspect analysis showed that south- and southeast-facing slopes (135°–180°) exhibited higher landslide density because of greater exposure to monsoon rainfall.

Distance to drainage emerged as another key factor; areas located within 100 m of streams or drainage channels contained nearly 65% of mapped landslide points.

Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) analysis demonstrated that bare land (12.5%) and settlement areas (18.4%) contributed most to slope failure, while forest cover (43%) acted as a natural stabilizer. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values ranged from -0.2 to 0.7, with low NDVI (<0.2) zones corresponding to unvegetated or degraded areas showing higher instability.

Rainfall data from the Bangladesh Meteorological Department indicated an annual average of 2,673 mm, and zones receiving rainfall above 2500 mm exhibited

the greatest number of landslide occurrences. Furthermore, areas within 200 m of road networks accounted for approximately 70% of total high-susceptibility pixels, confirming that slope cuts and improper drainage from road construction intensify instability risks.

3.2. Discussion

The findings align with previous research indicating that high-risk zones in the Rangamati district are concentrated in densely populated and topographically elevated areas. Consistent with Ahmed (2014), the integrated GIS-MCDA model proved robust for delineating susceptibility in the CHD. While earlier studies highlighted Rangamati Sadar as the most dangerous urban region, this research identifies Kaptai's high-altitude terrain and proximity to road networks as equally critical drivers of instability.

Conclusion

The GIS-AHP-based MCDA approach proved to be an efficient and systematic tool for assessing landslide susceptibility. The study identifies that **7.39%** of Kaptai Upazila is highly susceptible to landslides, primarily within the **Wagga, Chandraghona, and Kaptai** unions. These high-risk zones correlate with steep slopes exceeding 40° and historical landslide points identified near road networks. Moderate susceptibility covers the largest portion of the study area at **81.15%**, while low-risk areas account for **12.32%**. Despite the model's high spatial reliability and a **Kappa coefficient of 80%**, a significant limitation is the exclusion of lithology and soil depth factors due to data scarcity. Additionally, while AHP weights were validated by a **Consistency Ratio of 0.09**, they retain a degree of subjective expert judgment. Future research should incorporate real-time inventory validation and dynamic modeling to account for rapid anthropogenic land-use changes.

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Land Use Structure Efficiency in Bangladesh

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Keywords

Land use, SBM, Markov Transition, DMU

1. Introduction

In Bangladesh, one of the world's most densely populated nations, finite land resources are under immense strain from competing demands for agriculture, urbanization, and industry. This pressure threatens long-term food security, economic development, and environmental sustainability. While land use changes have been widely studied, a critical gap exists in understanding the efficiency of the overall land use structure - the output achieved from its optimal configuration. This study therefore aims to evaluate land use structure efficiency across Bangladesh by integrating economic benefits with environmental costs, providing a holistic assessment vital for the nation's sustainable development planning.

2. Materials and Methods

This study employed an integrated methodology to evaluate Land Use Structure Efficiency (LUSE) across all 64 districts of Bangladesh from 2018 to 2023. Each district was treated as a Decision-Making Unit (DMU) within a Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) framework. The core analytical tool was the non-parametric Slacks-Based Measure (SBM) model, specifically chosen for its ability to incorporate undesirable outputs, thus providing a holistic efficiency metric that balances economic benefits against environmental costs. The model was constructed using three categories of data. Input variables, representing land resources, were derived from the ESRI Global Land Use Land Cover dataset, quantifying areas of built-up, vegetation, waterbody, and barren land. Desirable outputs included district-level Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and electricity consumption, serving as proxies for economic and energy productivity. Undesirable outputs, accounting for environmental externalities, consisted of carbon and methane emissions, estimated using nighttime light data and land-cover-specific emission factors. The SBM model calculated an annual LUSE score for each district. To analyze temporal changes, these scores were discretized into efficiency

states, and a Markov chain analysis was applied to calculate transition probabilities, visualizing trends via a Sankey diagram. For spatial analysis, global and local Moran's I indices were computed to identify significant clustering patterns, such as high-high or low-low efficiency zones. This comprehensive approach, leveraging geospatial data and advanced modeling, quantitatively assessed the spatiotemporal dynamics of land use efficiency across Bangladesh.

3. Results and Discussion

The analysis revealed a pronounced and growing divergence in Land Use Structure Efficiency across Bangladesh. A stable cohort of districts, including Dhaka, Barishal, Khulna, and Rajshahi, consistently demonstrated high efficiency, successfully generating significant economic output relative to their land use inputs. In stark contrast, a persistent cluster of low-efficiency districts, such as Gopalganj, Shariatpur, and Jamalpur, remained trapped in a cycle of low productivity and high environmental externalities. Temporal analysis using Markov chains uncovered an alarming trend of entrenchment; the probability of a low-efficiency district remaining in that state increased dramatically from 63.16% to 88.89% over the study period, indicating a system where regional inequalities were becoming locked in. Spatially, Moran's I analysis confirmed significant clustering, with a consolidated high-high efficiency cluster in the southeastern region opposed by a low-low cluster of distress in the southwestern zone.

Fig 1: Land use structure Efficiency across Bangladesh (2018-2023)

Fig 2: Temporal variation through Sankey diagram

Fig 3: Spatial disparity through Moran's I

4. Conclusion

This study reveals that Bangladesh's land use structure is characterized by a critical and deepening divide. A stable group of high-efficiency districts—including Dhaka, Barishal, Khulna, and Rajshahi—generates high economic output from land resources. This is contrasted by a persistent cluster of low-efficiency districts, such as Gopalganj, Shariatpur, and Jamalpur, which remain trapped in a cycle of low productivity. Temporal analysis presents an alarming trend of entrenchment, with the probability of a low-efficiency district remaining inefficient rising from 63.16% to 88.89%, locking in regional inequalities. Spatially, this polarization is cemented by a significant high-high efficiency cluster in the southeast opposed by a low-low cluster in the southwest. These findings underscore an urgent need for spatially differentiated policies that boost productivity in lagging regions, manage environmental externalities in economic hubs, and break the cycle of disadvantage to steer Bangladesh toward a more balanced and sustainable land use future. This study is not without limitations. The analysis relies on projected GDP and emissions due to data availability constraints, which may introduce measurement uncertainty at the district level. Additionally, the five-year study window, while sufficient for trend detection, may not capture longer-term structural shifts. Future research should incorporate finer-resolution socioeconomic and environmental datasets, extend the temporal scope, and explore the causal drivers of efficiency divergence through panel econometric or simulation-based approaches. Comparative studies across

South Asian nations with similar land pressure profiles could further contextualize Bangladesh's land use challenges and inform regional policy frameworks.

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Comparative Spatio-Temporal Analysis and Forecasting of Aerosol Optical Depth in Khulna and Rajshahi Divisions (2001–2024)

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Keywords

Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), Spatio-Temporal analysis, vegetation cover, AOD Forecasting.

1. Introduction

Aerosols -tiny atmospheric particles - degrade air quality, affect human health, and influence climate. South Asia, including Bangladesh, experiences some of the world's highest aerosol loads from biomass burning, urban-industrial emissions and long-range dust transport (Ramanathan et al., 2001; Gautam et al., 2009). Despite extensive regional studies, long-term high-resolution MAIAC AOD₅₅₀ analysis for Khulna and Rajshahi remains limited, as do multi-model forecasts and assessments of AOD relationships with LST and NDVI. MAIAC MCD19A2 provides improved retrievals over Bangladesh's humid and heterogeneous landscapes. Khulna and Rajshahi represent contrasting coastal-humid and inland-dry environments, offering a meaningful basis for comparative aerosol assessment relevant to air-quality planning and environmental management. Objectives were to (i) quantify AOD trends and seasonal dynamics, (ii) classify aerosol types via AOD-Ångström rules, and (iii) develop and benchmark multi-model AOD forecasts (2025–2027).

2. Materials and Methods

Primary datasets include MODIS MAIAC MCD19A2 (AOD₅₅₀, 1 km daily) (Lyapustin & Wang, 2018), MODIS NDVI and LST products, CHIRPS precipitation, ERA5-Land (Wan, 2014). Data were acquired using Google Earth Engine, QA-filtered and harmonized to a 1 km grid. Aerosol particle size was inferred using the Ångström Exponent and classified (dust, urban/biomass, strong biomass burning, mixed, background) using an adapted AOD-AE rule set. Trend detection used Mann-Kendall and Sen's slope (Sen, 1968). For forecasting, SARIMAX (seasonal ARIMA with exogenous variables) to model linear seasonal dynamics, ETS to capture adaptive trend-seasonality patterns and Prophet for flexible trend and seasonal decomposition with changepoint handling. A Hybrid model combined

these approaches to enhance robustness. Exogenous predictors included air temperature, dew point, relative humidity, LST, NDVI, and wind components. Model selection used rolling-origin cross-validation (36-month training / 12-month testing) with RMSE, MAE and MAPE as evaluation metrics and 2024 served as the final out-of-sample validation year.

(1) NDVI

$$NDVI = \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{RED}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{RED}}$$

Where ρ_{NIR} is near-infrared reflectance (MODIS band 2) and ρ_{RED} is red reflectance (MODIS band 1).

(2) LST (Simplified split-window form)

$$T_s = T_{11} + A_1(T_{11} - T_{12}) + A_2(T_{11} - T_{12})^2 + A_0$$

Where T_s is land surface temperature (K); T_{11} and T_{12} are MODIS brightness temperatures in bands 31 and 32; A_0, A_1, A_2 are empirical coefficients that account for emissivity, emissivity difference, view angle and atmospheric water vapor.

(3) Ångström Exponent (two-wavelength, 440–870 nm)

$$AE_{440-870} = -\frac{\ln\left(\frac{AOD_{440}}{AOD_{870}}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{440}{870}\right)}$$

Where AOD₄₄₀ and AOD₈₇₀ are aerosol optical depths at 440 nm and 870 nm, respectively.

MAIAC/MODIS AOD uncertainties from clouds, bright surfaces, and algorithmic assumptions were minimized using quality flags, cloud/adjacent-cloud masking, and temporal-spatial filtering. Remaining uncertainties were acknowledged when interpreting trends and model outputs, with emphasis on relative and statistically robust patterns.

3. Results and Discussion

Analysis of annual AOD₅₅₀ from 2001 to 2024 indicates a significant long-term increase in aerosol loading in both Khulna and Rajshahi Divisions. Sen's slopes are 0.0108 yr⁻¹ for Khulna and 0.0094 yr⁻¹ for Rajshahi, corresponding to total increases of 64.1% and 44.3%, respectively.

Fig 1. Interannual AOD₅₅₀ trends (2001–2024) in Khulna and Rajshahi Divisions

Yearly AOD₅₅₀ maps show a clear expansion of High-Very High AOD₅₅₀ zones starting around 2008 in Khulna and 2009 in Rajshahi, rising from ~15% to ~35% after 2015. Seasonal peaks occur in the pre-monsoon (Rajshahi: 0.67; Khulna: 0.52) driven by biomass burning, while monsoon values are lowest due to rainfall cleansing (Khulna: 0.42; Rajshahi: 0.61). Winter is dominated by Urban/Biomass aerosols (Khulna ≈ 98.4%; Rajshahi ≈ 98%). Long-term trends indicate a significant increase in Anthropogenic/Urban-Biomass aerosols and a shift toward coarser particles (indicated by a decreasing Ångström Exponent) in both divisions.

From 2020–2024, the AOD–LST relationship strengthened - especially in Khulna ($r \approx 0.68$; $R^2 \approx 0.45-0.65$) indicating rising heat-linked aerosol loading, while the AOD–NDVI relationship has grown increasingly negative since 2010, reflecting vegetation stress from intensified emissions and biomass burning.

Forecasts for 2025–2027 indicate that AOD₅₅₀ levels will remain high, averaging 0.55–0.60 in Khulna and 0.60–0.65 in Rajshahi, reflecting the ongoing rising trend. Using the best-performing Prophet model, annual mean AOD in Khulna is projected at 0.673 (2025), 0.686 (2026), and 0.699 (2027), while Rajshahi shows slightly higher values of 0.698, 0.708, and 0.719, indicating continued elevated aerosol loading.

Fig 2. AOD₅₅₀ Forecasts Khulna Division (2025–2027): Multi Model Comparison

Fig 3. AOD₅₅₀ Forecasts Rajshahi Division (2025–2027): Multi Model Comparison

Moisture-related factors are the primary drivers in Khulna, with Dew Point Temperature playing the largest role (41.2% importance). In Rajshahi, LST and Dew Point Temperature hold significant influence (LST at 22% importance).

Conclusion

This study compared long-term AOD₅₅₀ trends, sources, and environmental links in Khulna and Rajshahi (2001–2024) and found a statistically significant increase in aerosol loading in both regions, driven primarily by anthropogenic sources (urban emissions and biomass burning). Khulna’s coastal system shows stronger sensitivity in AOD–LST–NDVI relationships, whereas Rajshahi has a higher pollution baseline with sharper seasonal peaks. By providing high-resolution trend data, identifying dominant drivers and delivering a validated forecasting framework, the study supplies actionable evidence for targeted regional policymaking and future air-quality management.

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Machine Learning Based Soil Organic Carbon Prediction with Remote Sensing in Khulna District

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Keywords

Soil Organic Carbon, Machine learning, Remote sensing, Shapley Additive Explanations.

1. Introduction

Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) is a key driver of soil productivity, fertility, and carbon sequestration to counter climate change. SOC dynamics in deltaic regions like Khulna, Bangladesh, are influenced by flooding, salinity, and varied land uses, making spatial prediction challenging. Field-based SOC surveys are accurate but spatially limited and time-consuming. Remote sensing and machine learning (ML) provides a scalable approach for fine-scale SOC prediction. Despite increasing applications of digital soil mapping, limited studies have examined SOC prediction in coastal deltaic environments using integrated radar–optical predictors (Guo et al., 2025). The objective of this study is to develop and evaluate machine-learning models for predicting topsoil SOC in Khulna using multi-source remote sensing and environmental predictors, and to assess the relative influence of terrain, vegetation, radar, and climate variables. The results yield a high-resolution SOC map that enables sustainable land management and carbon monitoring.

2. Materials and Methods

The methodological Framework shown in Figure 1. In total, 201 topsoil samples (0–20 cm) were collected across nine upazilas of Khulna District by the Soil Resource Development Institute (SRDI) in 2023. The 0–20 cm depth was selected as it represents the most biologically active soil layer and is commonly used in SOC monitoring studies. Each sample was geo-referenced and laboratory-tested for organic matter, and subsequently calculated to Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) using the Van Bemmelen factor (1.724). The data from the samples served as the dependent variable for model training and testing.

Predictor variables were extracted from multi-source datasets merged at 10 m spatial resolution using Google Earth Engine. Sentinel-2 optical data provided surface reflectance and vegetation indices (NDVI, SAVI, BSI), while Sentinel-1 radar data provided VV and VH backscatter values linked with soil moisture

and roughness. Topographic characteristics—slope, elevation, Topographic Ruggedness Index (TRI), and Topographic Wetness Index (TWI)—were derived from SRTM DEM, while mean annual temperature and precipitation were obtained from ERA5-Land reanalysis data.

Resampling and co-registration of layers to a common grid was performed. Selection of predictors applied Pearson correlation ($p < 0.05$), Variance Inflation Factor ($VIF < 10$), and correlation-matrix screening ($r < 0.80$) to remove redundancy. Machine-learning algorithms, i.e., Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Machine, and Multilayer Perceptron, were implemented in Python and cross-validated using k-fold cross-validation (Parvizi & Fatehi, 2025). Model performance was quantified using R^2 , RMSE, and MAE, and sensitivity analysis.

Fig 1. Methodological framework

3. Results and Discussion

Variable screening held a small, non-redundant set of predictors with high correlations to SOC. Pearson correlation revealed NDVI ($r = 0.651$), and Slope ($r = 0.621$) as the most informative ($p \leq 0.05$), and non-significant variables (e.g., NDMI, Aspect) were excluded. Multicollinearity filtering ($VIF > 10$) removed highly redundant predictors—most significantly SAVI ($VIF = 42.20$), VH (153.00)—leaving a balanced subset across

vegetation, radar, topography, and climate domains. The correlation matrix further reflected high pairwise collinearity (NDVI-SAVI $r = 0.99$), which led to final retention based on more direct SOC correlation and interpretability. Predictors selected for model use were NDVI, RED2, BSI, rainfall, temperature, VV backscatter,

elevation, slope, and TRI.

Fig 2. Random Forest feature importance with SHAP

Model performance suggested Random Forest (RF) to work best ($R^2 = 0.8129$), followed by Gradient Boosting (GB) ($R^2 = 0.7896$). SVM, MLP, and KNN lagged behind with lower R^2 and higher errors as seen in the composite score ranking (RF > GB > SVM > MLP > KNN). Sensitivity analysis ($\pm 10\%$ predictor perturbations) confirmed ensemble models' stability and determined individual controlling factors. GB was extremely sensitive to NDVI: a -10% perturbation increased RMSE by $+0.268$ and decreased R^2 by 0.094 , underlining the influence vegetation has on SOC prediction; RF showed moderate, evenly balanced change for vegetation and topography variables (e.g., Slope -10% : $\Delta RMSE = +0.066$).

Fig 3. Predictive maps from all model: RF, GB, SVM, KNN, MLP

Figure 2 illustrates model RF SHAP importance. SHAP importance analysis over models consistently ranked Slope and NDVI as greater SOC controls, with moderate control by VV and TRI. Slope (0.361) and NDVI (0.296) dominated RF; GB also ranked Slope (0.409) highest, followed by NDVI (0.222); SVM ranked Slope

(0.303) and TRI (0.198) highest; MLP ranked NDVI (0.723) and Slope (0.619) highest; Slope (0.267) and TRI (0.250) ranked highest of all in KNN. In combination, terrain and vegetation cues were first-order controls of SOC in the study area.

Spatially, RF-based SOC map depicted a clear south-north gradient in Khulna District with values of 0.6% to 15%. (Figure 3). Coastal upazilas such as Koyra and Dacope had the highest SOC contents (mean $\geq 8\%$) owing to tidal sedimentation and good cover of vegetation, whereas SOC was lower in the inland upazilas such as Paikgachha and Dumuria (3–5%) due to widespread cultivation. Around 6% of the district was highly SOC ($> 12\%$), and most zones were in low to medium ranges. Forest (8.35%) and rangeland (7.57%) contained highest SOC content, followed by flooded vegetation (5.64%), whereas croplands ($\sim 4.9\%$) and urban/built-up areas (5–6%) recorded large losses owing to land-use pressure and lower organic inputs (Rahman et al.,2021).

Conclusion

This research developed a machine learning-guided model for predicting and mapping Khulna District's topsoil Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) using Sentinel-1 SAR, Sentinel-2 optical, topographic, and climatic inputs. Of five algorithms, Random Forest exhibited the highest accuracy ($R^2 \approx 0.81$), and slope, NDVI, terrain features, and radar backscatter were recognized as major SOC controls. The resulting 10-m SOC map provides a valuable baseline for carbon-stock estimation, soil fertility management, land-use planning, and carbon-monitoring in deltaic settings. By illustrating the union of radar and optical data with environmental covariates, this research contributes to an extension of a scalable approach of digital soil mapping.

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Climate Change Induced Future Flood Probability Mapping In Bangladesh

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Keywords

Random Forest Model, Artificial Neural Network, SVM, CatBoost model, climate change, CMIP5, RCP scenarios, remote sensing, GIS, machine learning, flood probability mapping, flood risk management

1. Introduction

Bangladesh, a low-lying deltaic country at the meeting point of the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna river systems, is one of the world's most flood-prone areas. Rising temperatures, unpredictable monsoon rainfall, and more intense extreme weather events are all signs of rapid climate change that are making floods more frequent, severe, and longer-lasting. This poses serious risks to infrastructure, livelihoods, and sustainable development. Against this backdrop, the current study integrated Remote Sensing (RS), Geographic Information Systems (GIS), and Machine Learning (ML) within a CMIP5 climate scenario environment in order to construct a climate change-based future flood probability mapping framework.

2. Materials and Methods

Backscatter difference techniques in Google Earth Engine (GEE) were used to extract annual flood inundation patterns using multi-temporal satellite datasets from Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) and Landsat-8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) covering the period 2015– 2024. To estimate flood vulnerability, a number of topographic, meteorological, and environmental conditioning elements were included, such as elevation, slope, precipitation, land use/land cover (LULC), NDVI, land surface temperature (LST), soil type, and river proximity.

Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and CatBoost (CB) are four supervised machine learning methods that were used and assessed using accuracy. With an AUC of 0.93, which indicates exceptional prediction ability and model stability, CatBoost performed the best among them. Future flood probabilities for 2050, 2075, and 2100 were then simulated using the validated CatBoost model under four Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6.0, and RCP8.5) and downscaled climate projections from the

Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5).

Fig 1. Methodological Framework

Flood-susceptible zones gradually expanded, according to the results, with the highest increases taking place under the high-emission RCP8.5 (SSP585) scenario. It is predicted that by 2100, about one-third of Bangladesh would have a very high likelihood of flooding (≥ 0.8), especially in the southern coastal delta regions, central floodplains, and northeastern haor basins.

3. Results and Discussion

The goal of this study was to create a flood probability mapping framework for Bangladesh, one of the world's most flood-vulnerable nations, based on climate change. In order to evaluate current and future flood susceptibility under changing climatic circumstances, the study combines Remote Sensing (RS), Geographic Information Systems (GIS), and Machine Learning (ML) methodologies. The main objective was to provide spatially explicit, scientifically based flood probability maps that might guide policy decisions, flood management, and climate-resilient planning.

The study examined the spatial-temporal trends of floods in Bangladesh from 2015 to 2024 using climate records, environmental characteristics, and multi-temporal satellite images. A thorough collection of predictor variables was used to train and validate four supervised machine learning algorithms: Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), and CatBoost (CB). Of them, CatBoost demonstrated the best predicted accuracy

(AUC = 0.93) and stability, demonstrating its exceptional ability to manage heterogeneous data types and intricate nonlinear interactions.

Fig 2. Roc Curve of Training Data Vs Testing Data of (A) ANN, (B) SVM, (C) Random Forest, (D) CATBOOST

The CMIP5 climate models were used to create future estimates, simulating future emission trajectories using Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs). Conceptually, the RCPs employed in this work match the SSP-based maps shown in the PowerPoint: A low-emission sustainable development scenario is represented by SSP1–2.6, a moderate stabilization pathway by SSP2–4.5, intermediate emissions with limited mitigation by RCP6.0 (SSP3–7.0), and a high-emission, fossil fuel-intensive growth trajectory by SSP5–8.5. Maps of the likelihood of flooding were created for the near-, mid-, and long-term climate scenarios of 2050, 2075, and 2100.

Fig 3. Long-Term Climate Scenarios Of 2050, 2075, And 2100

The findings showed that, especially under high-emission scenarios, high flood probability zones gradually spread throughout Bangladesh towards the end of the

twenty-first century (RCP8.5/SSP585). By 2100, about one-third of the country's land might be at very high risk of flooding (>0.8 likelihood) under this extreme scenario. In the context of the nation's dynamic deltaic geography, the findings offer an early warning basis for climate-adaptive land-use planning, resilient infrastructure, and sustainable water resource management.

4. Conclusion

This study uses remote sensing, GIS, and machine learning within a CMIP5 climate framework to assess and predict flood risk in Bangladesh. The CatBoost model was highly accurate (AUC = 0.93), identifying critical parameters such as elevation, NDVI, precipitation, and river proximity as primary causes of floods. The findings reveal an increase in flood severity (2015- 2024) and suggest that by 2100, up to one-third of Bangladesh may face very high flood risk under high- emission scenarios. The generated flood maps can help influence policy, planning, and climate adaptation activities, such as the Bangladesh Delta Plan 2100.

Despite data and modelling constraints, the methodology lays the groundwork for data-driven, proactive flood control to help Bangladesh become more climate resilient.

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Assessing Cyclone Impact and Recovery Utilizing Nighttime Light Data in Bangladesh

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Keywords

Nighttime light, Cyclone impact, Disaster recovery, Remote Sensing, Bangladesh

1. Introduction

Bangladesh's geographic location makes it one of the world's most cyclone-prone countries, frequently suffering from significant infrastructural damage and economic disruption (Mallick & Vogt, 2014). Over the decades, the country has endured some of the world's most devastating tropical cyclones such as Bulbul (2019), Amphan (2020), Sitrang (2022), Mocha (2023) and Remal (2024), each leaving behind widespread human and economic losses. In Bangladesh, post-disaster assessment and recovery monitoring processes remain inadequate. Traditional assessment methods are often time-consuming, costly, and limited in scale. Nighttime Light (NTL) data has emerged as a powerful proxy for monitoring human activity and the operational status of infrastructure, offering a rapid and large-scale alternative for impact assessment (Lin et al., 2023). The brightness of nighttime lights reflects levels of economic activity and electrification, making significant drops in NTL radiance a key indicator of disaster-induced disruption. This study aims to harness daily NTL data to quantitatively assess the impact and subsequent recovery patterns of major cyclones that have struck the coastal regions of Bangladesh, providing a novel framework for near-real-time disaster monitoring.

2. Materials and Methods

The study used the NOAA VIIRS-DNB (Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite - Day/Night Band) monthly composite dataset accessed via Google Earth Engine (GEE). Monthly NTL data reduce cloud cover and noise effects, ensuring more stable and reliable radiance measurements. The dataset provides radiance values (in nanowatts/cm²/sr) representing nighttime brightness. The methodology included the following steps:

Baseline Establishment: A pre-cyclone baseline was defined by averaging NTL radiance over the month immediately preceding each cyclone's landfall.

Impact Assessment: The impact was calculated as the percentage drop in NTL radiance between the baseline and the cyclone month (May). The formula used:

$$\text{Impact (\%)} = \frac{\text{Baseline} - \text{Cyclone Month}}{\text{Baseline}} \times 100$$

This captures the spatial extent of blackout and infrastructure loss.

Recovery Analysis: Post-cyclone NTL values were tracked monthly for up to six months to estimate the Recovery Rate (RR):

$$\text{Recovery Rate} = \frac{\text{NTL}_t - \text{NTL}_{\min}}{\text{Baseline} - \text{NTL}_{\min}}$$

where, NTL_t is the radiance at month t and NTL_{min} is the lowest post-disaster value.

Zonal Statistics and Correlation: District level mean NTL values were extracted and correlated with official ground data from the Department of Disaster Management (DDM) including the percentage of population affected, houses damaged, and storm surge areas to validate the satellite-derived impact metrics.

3. Results and Discussion

The results reveal a strong quantitative relationship between cyclone intensity and NTL reduction across affected regions of Bangladesh. Cyclone Mocha produced the most severe disruption, with an 85.1% decrease in nighttime radiance in Cox's Bazar, representing near-total blackout conditions. Super Cyclone Amphan caused an average 78.5% reduction across Satkhira, Khulna, and Bagerhat, while Cyclone Remal generated a 62.3% decrease in its core impact zone. Cyclone Sitrang showed a comparatively moderate but significant 45.2% maximum reduction in Bhola and Noakhali. Recovery analysis demonstrated marked temporal disparities: Sitrang-affected regions returned to 95% of baseline brightness within 15-25 days, Remal required 30-40 days, and Amphan needed 45-60 days for restoration in the worst-hit districts. In the case of Mocha, Cox's Bazar city recovered substantially within 20 days, yet rural and hilly areas remained below 70% of pre-cyclone illumination even

after 50 days. These findings confirm that NTL data effectively quantify both immediate impact magnitude and differential recovery trajectories, while also exposing pronounced urban-rural inequalities in post-disaster restoration.

Overall, the study confirms that NTL data provides a reliable proxy for post-disaster evaluation, especially in regions where field-based monitoring is challenging or delayed.

Fig 1: Impact of Cyclone Amphan: (a) Before, (b) After

Fig 2: Impact of Cyclone Mocha: (a) Before, (b) After

Fig 3: Impact of Cyclone Remal: (a) Before, (b) After

Fig 4: Impact of Cyclone Sitrang: (a) Before, (b) After

4. Conclusion

This research establishes a comprehensive framework for using Nighttime Light (NTL) data to assess cyclone impacts and monitor recovery across Bangladesh. The findings confirm a strong relationship between cyclone intensity and nighttime radiance reduction, with severe storms such as Mocha causing near-total black-outs (85.1% reduction in Cox’s Bazar). The study also highlights pronounced urban-rural recovery disparities, as urban centers recovered much faster than surrounding rural areas, revealing structural inequalities in infrastructure resilience and resource allocation. Validation with ground data supports the reliability of NTL as a disaster assessment tool, particularly when high-quality verification data are available. Beyond impact measurement, the framework offers practical value for rapid damage identification, recovery monitoring, and evidence-based resource prioritization. Although limitations remain especially in non-electrified areas the integration of NTL analysis into national disaster management systems can strengthen equitable recovery planning, resilience building, and long-term climate adaptation strategies in Bangladesh.

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Volume 2

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